

Catalogue of subtribe *Bembidiina* of former Yugoslavia (Coleoptera Carabidae *Bembidiini*)

PAOLO BONAVIDA¹ AND DRAGAN PAVIČEVIĆ²

¹ Via Pico 14, 00189 Roma, Italy
e-mail: paolo.bonavita60@gmail.com

² Krunska 15, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia
e-mail: dragan.pavicevic@hotmail.com

INTRODUCTION

Since the last catalogue of more than 20 years ago on Carabidae of former Yugoslavia (Drovenik & Peks, 1999) further changes occurred in the systematics and distributions; in this paper we report the updated knowledge about the subtribe *Bembidiina*.

The results are reported in this catalogue of *Bembidiina* for all current States derived from the break-up of the former Yugoslavia: Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Serbia, Montenegro, and North Macedonia.

The material examined come from the following collections: collections Nonveiller and Pavičević (Dpa); Natural History Museum Belgrade (MB); Gianni Allegro (All), Paolo Bonavita (Bon), Achille Casale (Cas), Giorgio Colombetta (Col), Werner Marggi (Mar), Paolo Neri (Ner), Maurizio Pavesi (Pav), Karel Rebl (Reb), Luca Toledano (CTVR).

Acronyms: SLO – Slovenia; CRO – Croatia; SB – Serbia; BH – Bosnia-Herzegovina; MTG – Montenegro; NMA – North Macedonia. All specimens with ! were directly identified.

We avoid reporting the original data cited in Čurčić et al. (2007). Also for Bonavita & Vigna Taglianti (2010), Hristovki & Guéorguiev (2015) and Hristovski et al. (2016) we don't report all data and citations, and so we refer to these works for original data. The data of Drovenik & Peks (1999) are reported only when different from those of Drovenik & Peks (1994). Besides, we cite Vigna Taglianti (2004) and Marggi et al. (2017) only in the absence of other data with specific localities.

The distributions and the chorotypes refer to the species. In the catalogue the genera are in systematic order following Maddison (2012), while the species are in alphabetic order.

The chorotypes of the species generally follow Vigna Taglianti et al. (1993, 1999); relatively to the specific fauna of the Balkan, we added the subchorotypes BAN, for the species with distribution Balkano-Anatolian and attributable to the chorotype TUM (Turano-Mediterranean) (Vigna Taglianti et al., 1999: 35), and the subchorotype BALK, for the endemic species of Balkans, attributable to the chorotype SEU (S-European) (Vigna Taglianti et al., 1999: 36).

The photographs of the habitus, made by our colleague Luca Toledano, that we thank here, are composite images with progressive focusing obtained with a AmScope 18 MP USB 3.0 Color CMOS Microscope Camera mounted on a Leica Z6 microscope equipped with a 1.0x Leica lens and a customized motorized stand made by LT, then processed with Helicon Focus® 6.4.3 and optimized with Photoshop® Elements 14.

We dedicate this work to the memory of Prof. Guido Nonveiller (Rijeka, 1913 - Zemun, 2002); he was professor of entomology at the Agricultural Faculty in Zemun (Serbia). He dealt with entomology from an early age and was a friend of P. Novak and G. Müller. It is worth mentioning that he spent the Second World War in France as one of the leaders of the movement called “Resistance” and returned to Yugoslavia after the war.

CATALOGUE

tribe Bembidiini Stephens, 1827

subtribe Bembidiina Stephens, 1827

Sinechostictus Motschulsky, 1864

subg. *Sinechostictus* Motschulsky, 1864

1. *S. (Sinechostictus) decoratus* (Duftschmid, 1812)

Netolitzky (1926): BH - Travnik, (in letter by Meschnigg: Jablanika, Ivanplanina).

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Bled; Podkraj pri Hrastniku, Sava.

Drovenik & Peks (1994) – SLO (Nord)

Distribution: SLO - BH

Chorotype: CEU

? *S. (Sinechostictus) kosti* (Matits, 1912)

The real identity of this species, known only by description, is not clear. The

collection of Matits is can not be found.

Distribution: SB

2. *S. (Sinechostictus) millerianus* (Heyden, 1883)

SERBIA

Šar planina, Čop, m 1000, 16.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Šar planina, Durlov potok, nm 1500m, 20.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 7 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Zvonačka Banja, Prskalo, nm 520m, 25.IV.2002, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Šar planina, Durlov Potok, nm 1700 m, 20.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Arilje-Moravica, 20.5.1991, V. Zieris lgt., 2 ♂♂ (CTVR)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Hercegovina, Zvezda, Olovo, 24.6.1987 Jaroslav Jelinek lgt. 1 ♀ (CTVR)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonia, Šar Planina, Popova Šapka 27-28.VI.1965, G. Pozzi Como, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Čevljanović bei Sarajevo, Krupatal bei Pazarić in Gesellschaft des *B. ruficorne*, Vrbasfluss bei Gornji Vakuf.

Netolitzky & Meyer (1933a): SLO – Solcava, Savin. Alp. Storič; BH – Bosnien, Igbartal, Maglič.

Netolitzky (1943): BH

Müller-Motzfeld (1982): SLO – Krajska-Gora.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994) – SLO – BH – SB - MTG (Murino) - NMA

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities.

Guéorguiev (2011): CRO

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015) : NMA – more localities.

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – more localities

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH - SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: CEU

Notes. All bibliographic data reported below for *S. ruficornis* except for SLO, could refer to this species.

3. *S. (Sinechostictus) ruficornis* (Sturm, 1825)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Umgebung von Sarajevo, Krupatal bei Pazarič, Han

Koprivnica bei Kupreš.

Müller (1926): SLO – Ludaria, lungo l’Isonzo tra Plesso e Caporetto, Tolmino, Volzana (Volče), Bochnia presso la cascata della Savizza

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994) – SLO – BH - MTG (Murino) - NMA (Sar planina)

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities

Notes. Before the work of Müller-Motzfeld (1982) this species was often confused with *S. millerianus*. So, all old data need a revision. We identified as *S. millerianus* all specimens seen from Serbia, and we suspect that *S. ruficornis* doesn’t occur in Balkan Peninsula (see also Hristovki & Guéorguiev, 2015: 63), with his limits in the Alps.

Distribution: SLO - ?BH – ?SB - ?MTG - ?NMA

Chorotype: CEU

4. *S. (Sinechostictus) stomoides* (Dejean, 1831)

ssp. *stomoides* (Dejean, 1831)

Apfelbeck (1904): CRO - Ivanščica-Gebirge bei Varaždin.

Netolitzky & Meyer (1932c sub *atroviolaceum* Duf.): CRO – Papuk-Gebirge und Varaždin, Vinkovci.

Drovenik & Peks (1994) – SLO – CRO (Ivanščica)

Distribution: SLO – CRO

Chorotype: CEU

5. *S. (Sinechostictus) tarsicus* (Peyron, 1858)

SLOVENIA

YU, Slovenija, VM62, Kamniška ˘ka Bistrica Kamnik, 1.V.1984, leg. B.

Drovenik, 4 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Mar)

Slovenija, Robic, greto f. Natisone 18/VIII/97, Leg. P. De Martin, 4 ♂♂, 4 ♀ (CTVR)

CROATIA

Env. de Zagreb, Alluivo Save, 12.IV.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(MB)

SERBIA

Serbia, Pirot env. dol. riek., Jerme, na brehu, 28.IV.2002, leg. T. Jászay, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(MB, Bon)

Srbija, Kruševac, Obilčevo-Rasina, Parunovac, 4.V.1934, leg. S. Svirčev, 1

♂!(Dpa)

Serbia, Pirot env. dol. riek., Jerme, na brehu, 28.IV.2002, leg. T. Jászay, 1

♂!(Bon)

Yugoslavia, Katun, Niš, 23.V.1981, leg. G. Sama, 1 ♂!(Pav)

Srbija, Arilje-Moravica, 20.5.1991, V. Zieris lgt., 1 ♂♂, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

NORTH MACEDONIA

YU, Macedonia, Mavrovo, 27.V.1976, leg. G. Sama, 2 ♀♀!(Pav)

MONTENEGRO

YU, Crna Gora, Skadarsko I., Virpazar env., 7.vii.2002, P. Bulirsch lgt. 1 ♀ (CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *elongatum*): BH – CRO – Knin; MTG – Rjeka, Podgorica; SB – Niš, Negotin, Surdulica bei Vranja.

Müller (1926 sub *elongatum*): SLO – lungo il Timavo sup. a Mali Pristava e Loke, Risano; CRO - presso Zaule, dint. Fiume (Val Recina).

Netolitzky & Meyer (1932a): SLO – Pettau, Steinbrück, Montpreis, Kalobje, Sv. Jakob, Sv. Jurij, Podčetrtek, Lichtenwald [Sednica], Radna und St. Paul, Laibach; CRO – Agram, Sušak, Rečinal, Castelnuovo; BH – Celič, Rrčka, Bosn. Brod, Ilidže, Prozor, Nemile und Majevica, Travnik, Sarajevo, Trebinje, Vruja; MTG – “Ursprung in Montenegro“.

Drovenik (1994 sub *elongatum tarsicum*): SLO – Perovo pri Kamniku, Kamniška Bistrica; Podkraj pri Hrastniku, Sava.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *elongatum tarsicum*): SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Ćurčić et al. (2007 sub *elongatum*): SB – many localities.

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015) : NMA – many localities.

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: TUM (BAN)

subg. *Pseudolimnaeum* Kraatz, 1888

6. *S. (Pseudolimnaeum) doderoi* (Ganglbauer, 1891)

SLOVENIA

Styria mer., Solcava, VIII.1931, leg. Cepic, 1 ♂ imm.!(MB)

SERBIA

Serb., Majdanpek, 15.V.1979, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Serb., T. Užice, Rožanstvo, Stopića peć., 26.V.1978, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

NORTH MACEDONIA

S. Makedonija, Bistra pl., klisura Radike, M. Sv. Jovan Bogorski, 18.IV.2000, leg. I. Karaman, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

S. Makedonia, Bistra pl., klisura Radike, M. Sv. Jovan Bigorski, 18.IV.2000, leg. I. Karaman, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

S. Makedonia, Šar pl., Suva Reka m 1200, 23.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

S. Makedonia, klisura Radike, Manastir, Sv. Jovan Bigorski, 18.IV.2000, leg. I. Karaman, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Müller (1926): SLO – Aidussina, Carniola (Bochinia).

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Kokra; Vaniše, Menina planina; Košenjak; Podkraj pri Hrastniku, Sava.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - Cro (Da) - SB (Strbce) - MTG (Prokletije) - NMA (Bistra planina)

Guéorguiev (2011): BH

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – more bibliographic data

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities.

Distribution: SLO - CRO – BH - SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: CEU

7. *S. (Pseudolimnaeum) inustus* (Jacquelin du Val, 1857)

Müller (1926): SLO - Bochinia (lungo la Savizza).

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Podkraj pri Hrastniku, Sava.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO

Distribution: SLO

Chorotype: CEU

Ocys Stephens, 1828

8. *Ocys harpaloides* (Audinet-Serville, 1821)

CROATIA

Hrvatska, Velebit, Paklenica, Devnjača, 1.VIII.2001, leg. S. V. Karlo, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Plasa planina, Höhlen bei Drieno unweit Trebinje; MTG – Castelnuovo, Rjeka.

Netolitzky (1916a): CRO – Zara; MTG - Castelnuovo in Bocche di Cattaro; BH – Mostar, Drijeno bei Trebinje, (Apfelbeck, 1904: Plasa planina).

Müller (1926): SLO – Ospos; CRO – Zaule, dint. Fiume, Val Recina presso Lopazza, Isola Arbe.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - CRO – BH (H) - MTG

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – Mt. Avala.

Distribution: SLO - CRO – BH – SB - MTG

Chorotype: EUM

9. *Ocys hoffmanni* (Netolitzky, 1917)

Species know only by the original description, from Dalmatia (Biokovogebirge).

Distribution: CRO

Chorotype: SEU (BALK)

10. *Ocys quinquestriatus* (Gyllenhal, 1810)

ssp. *quinquestriatus* (Gyllenhal, 1810)

SERBIA

Srbija, pl Beljanica 1160 m, 12.VIII.1995, leg. D. Pavićević, 1 ex.!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Muharnica pl., m 1400-1500, 12.V.1931, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Prenj planina

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - CRO – BH (H)

Distribution: SLO - CRO – BH – SB

Chorotype: EUR

Notes. Species new for Serbia.

11. *Ocys reticulatus* (Netolitzky, 1917)

ssp. *reticulatus* (Netolitzky, 1917)

Depoli (1930 sub *quinquestriatum reticulatum* Net.): CRO - M. Maggiore (in vetta sotto un sasso)

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO (Malerija) - CRO (Ucka) - SB (Strbce) – MTG - NMA (Tetovo)

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – Štrpce

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015) : NMA – some bibliographic data

ssp. *croaticus* (Müller, 1943)

Müller G. (1943): CRO – Monte Santo nei Velebit, Grotta di Samograd nella Lika.

Distribution: SLO - CRO - SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: SEU

Notes. The subspecies *reticulatus* and *croaticus* need to be reviewed; the finding of *croaticus* within the distribution of *reticulatus* seems incoherent.

Asaphidion Gozis, 1886

12. *Asaphidion austriacum* Schweiger, 1975

Schweiger (1975): SLO - Wurzenpass S-Hang, Umg. Bled, Murauen bei Radenci.

Drovenik & Peks (1994) – SLO

Allegro (in letter): SLO (Trenta, leg. Muilwijk)

Distribution: SLO

Chorotype: CEU

13. *Asaphidion caraboides* (Schrank, 1781)

Netolitzky (1918b): SLO – Flitsch-Karfreit, Laibach, Moistrana; CRO – Agram.

Müller (1926): SLO - S. Lucia, Volzana (Volče)

Drovenik & Peks (1994) – SLO

Distribution: SLO

Chorotype: CEU

14. *Asaphidion cyanicorne* (Pandellè, 1867)

ssp. *cyanicorne* (Pandellè, 1867)

= *quarnerense* Schatzmayr, 1914

Müller (1926): CRO – isola di Unie, Arbe, Pola
 Drovenik & Peks (1994) – CRO (Kvarnerc Inseln)

Distribution: CRO
 Chorotype: CEU

15. *Asaphidion curtum* (Heyden, 1870)
 ssp. *curtum* (Heyden, 1870)

Distribution: SLO
 Chorotype: WME

Notes. Vigna Taglianti (2004) mentions this species from Slovenia; we don't know any data.

16. *Asaphidion flavipes* (Linnaeus, 1760)

CROATIA

Zagreb Cro, Savica, VI.1930, leg. Svirčev, 2 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)
 Sinj Dalm., 28.IV.1914, leg. Novak, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Bon)

SERBIA

V. Gradiste, 20.V.1957, leg. Stančić, 3 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀!(MB, Bon)
 Srbija, Jelavci, nm 480 m, 18.VI.2001, leg. B. Blesić, 1 ♂!(Dpa)
 Srbija, Topola, 28.V.1989, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
 Srbija, Guča, Krnaca, 28.VIII.2002, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
 Srbija, Beograd, 18.V-1.VI.2003, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)
 Srbija, Kruševac, IV.1934, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
 Srbija, Kruševac, Obilicevo, 5.IV.1934, leg. G. Nonveiller, 5 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)
 Srbija, Planina Bukulja 19.VI.1955, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
 Požeženo, V. Gradište Serb., 13.V.1955, leg. Stančić, 1 ♀!(MB)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Mostar Herz., V.1928, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)
 Tribrod Serb., V. Gradište, 24.IX.1954, leg. Stančić, 1 ♂!(MB)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – gemein; SB – Majdan Kutšajna, Negotin, Golubac, Požarevac.

Müller (1926): SLO - lungo il Risano pr. Capodistria; CRO – Quietto presso Levade, dint. di Fiume in Val Recina, nel bosco di Capofronte all'isola di Arbe.

Depoli (1930): CRO - Valle d. Recina.
Focarile (1964): BH - Jablanica; CRO - Metcovich, Zara.
Drovenik & Peks (1994) - SLO - CRO - BH - SB - NMA
Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB - many localities
Guéorguiev (2011): MTG
Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): MA: many localities
Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA - many localities

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH - SB - MTG - NMA
Chorotype: SIE

17. *Asaphidion nebulosum* (P. Rossi, 1792)
ssp. *balcanicum* Netolitzky, 1918

CROATIA

F. Narenta, Metković, 22.7.87 Monguzzi, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *caraboides*): BH - verbreitet, an schattigen Flussufern;
MTG - Rjeka; SB - MajdanKučajna, Negotin, Tekija
Müller (1926 sub *nebulosum*): sponda del Quieto pr. Levade.
Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *nebulosum*) - CRO (Da)
Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *caraboides balcanicum*) - BH - SB - NMA
Ćurčić et al. (2007 sub *caraboides*): SB - many localities
Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): MA: many localities
Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA - more localities

Distribution: CRO - BH - SB - MTG - NMA
Chorotype: SEU

Notes. The ssp. *nebulosum* is known only from Italian peninsula (Bonavita & Vigna Taglianti, 2005), while in the oriental Alps only the conspecific *A. caraboides* occurs; so, the specimen cited by Müller should refer to ssp. *balcanicum*.

18. *Asaphidion pallipes* (Duftschmid, 1812)

SLOVENIA

Trenta, [leg.] Muilwjik (All)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH - mit Vorigem; SB - Požarevac.
Müller (1926): SLO - Sonzia, Tolmino, Volzana (Volče), S. Lucia, cascata della Savizza.

Drovenik & Peks (1994) – SLO – BH – SB
 Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Distribution: SLO - BH – SB
 Chorotype: SIE

19. *Asaphidion stierlini* (Heyden, 1880)

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA: Demir Kapija canyon, near Bela Voda cave,

Distribution: NMA
 Chorotype: MED

Bembidion Latreille, 1802

subg. *Phyla* Motschulsky, 1844

20. *B. (Phyla) obtusum* Audinet-Serville, 1821

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities.

Distribution: SB
 Chorotype: WME

Notes. From the map of Huber & Marggi (1997) this species seems to occur also in Slovenia, but in the text there are no detailed indications of any localities.

21. *B. (Phyla) tethys* Netolitzky, 1926

CROATIA

Croatia, Solin, 28.IV.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Solin, 8.IX.1925, leg. G. Nonveiller, 6 ♂♂!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Dalmatia, Solin, 24.VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *obtusum*, according to Huber & Marggi, 1997): BH – Domanović; CRO – Zara.

Müller (1926): CRO – Pola, Brioni, Scoglio Pomer piccolo nel porto di Medolino, Scoglio Fenara presso il Capo Promontore, Lussin (località Curilla),

Unie.

Depoli (1930 sub *obtusum Tethys* Net.): CRO - Lussin (Curilla).

Drovenik & Peks (1994): CRO (Da) – BH – SB – MTG

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – Serbia, without precise locality.

Distribution: CRO – BH – SB - MTG

Chorotype: MED

subg. *Eupetedromus* Netolitzky, 1911

22. B. (*Eupetedromus*) *dentellum* (Thunberg, 1787)

SLOVENIA

Slovenija, Postojna Planina, sponde fiume Unica, 20/V/90, Leg. P. De Martin, 42 ♂♂, 36 ♀♀ (CTVR)

Slovenija, Lago di Cerknica q.500, 19-20/V/90, Leg. P. De Martin, 7 ♂♂, 15 ♀♀ (CTVR)

CROATIA

Hrvatska, Zagreb, Savica, V.1944, leg. S. Svirčev, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂ imm.!(Dpa Dpa))

Maksimir, env. de Zagreb, 4.VIII.1943, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Srbija, Beograd, Miljackovačka šuma, 8.V.1992, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ex !(Dpa)

Srem, Zemun, kej, 3.X.1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, , 2 ex. !(Dpa)

Syrmium Zemun, 12.VIII.1942, leg. Ing. Osterman, 1 ♂!(MB)

Syrmium Zemun, 22.IV.1942, leg. Ing. Osterman, 1 ♂!(MB)

Serb., Kruševac, env. Obilićevo, 12.VII.1934, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent, Bugojno, Reljevo bei Sarajevo; SB – Požarevac, Milanovac, Golubac, Negotin.

Müller (1926): SLO - lago di Zirknitz (Carniola)

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - CRO (Rijeka) - BH (B) – SB - MTG (Biogradsko jezero)

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB - MTG

Chorotype: SIE

23. *B. (Eupetedromus) starkii* Schaum, 1860

SLOVENIA

Styria, Maribor, 10.IV.1930, Freisraben, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(MB, Bon)

CROATIA

Croatia NW, Ivanščica Mts., Ivanec env., 9.VI.2011, R. Krause lgt., K. Rébl det., 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀ (Reb)

Apfelbeck (1904): CRO – Ludbreg bei Varasdin

Netolitzky (1913b): CRO - BH - Prjedor

Netolitzky (1943): CRO – BH

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Kalobje

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO (Maribor) - CRO (Ludbreg)

Guéorguiev (2011): BH

Marggi et al. (2017) - SLO

Distribution: SLO - CRO – BH

Chorotype: CEU

subg. *Philochthus* Stephens, 1828**24. *B. (Philochthus) biguttatum* (Fabricius, 1779)**

SLOVENIA

Slovenija, Postojna Planina, sponde fume Unica, 20/V/90, Leg. P. De Martin, 3 ♂♂, 8 ♀♀ (CTVR)

Slovenija, Lago di Cerknica q.500, 19-20/V/90, Leg. P. De Martin, 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀ (CTVR)

SERBIA

Srbija, Beograd, VIII.2001, leg. A. Zatezalo, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Reitter (1885): BH - “am Ufer der Bosna”.

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent, Han Koprivnica bei Kupreš.

Müller (1926): SLO - Ribnica al Timavo sup., Prevallo.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Cerkniško jezero (Ušiva loka, Karlovica)

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – BH (B)

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – Grebenac; Deliblato Sands

Guéorguiev (2011): CRO

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015) : NMA - more localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – Skopska Crna Gora, s. Brazda, Čardak, dolni Sv. Ilija

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH – SB – NMA

Chorotype: SIE

25. *B. (Philochthus) decolor* Apfelbeck, 1911

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, Bar, 1 ex.!(MB)

Netolitzky (1943): MTG - Castelnuovo.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): CRO (Metkovic) - BH (H) - MTG (Ulcinj).

Müller-Motzfeld & Marggi (2009): MTG – Ulcinj, Castelnuovo.

Distribution: CRO - BH - MTG

Chorotype: EME

Notes. Neri & Gudenzi (2013) mention this species only for Montenegro and not for Croatia and Bosnia-Herzegovina.

26. *B. (Philochthus) guttula* (Fabricius, 1792)

SERBIA

Srbija, Zlatibor, kod Pipalske, pećine, 10.VIII.2002, leg. D.Pavičević, 3 ♂♂, 11 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Sjenica, Ursule, Baždarska peć. 1020 m, 30.VIII.2002/13.V.2003, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Sjenica, S. Ušak, Ušacka peć., 30.VIII.2002/15.V.2003, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent, Travnik, Sarajevo, Višegrad; MTG – Podgorica.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO (Lenart bei Maribor) – CRO (Lika, Veliki Skocaj) - BH (B) - MTG (Titograd)

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015) : NMA – Demir Kapija; Kožuf, Boshava River, 700m, near Konopishte Village.

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – Demir Kapija

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH - SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: SIE

27. *B. (Philochthus) inoptatum* Schaum, 1857

SLOVENIA

SW Slovenia, Ljubiana 25 km S, Cerknisko lake, 14.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj,
1 ♂, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

CROATIA

Hrvatska, Zagreb, Savica, V.1944, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Env. de Zagreb, Maksimir, 16.IV.1944, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 5.VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Solin, VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Maksimir, 16.IV.1944, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)

SERBIA

Zemun, Serb., 1 ex.!(MB)

Srbija, Zemun, 26.VI.1935, leg G. Nonveiller, 5 ♀♀ (3 imm.)(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Niš, Kalafat, village Kopajkošara, pećina Samar, 18.VI.2001, leg. S. Ognjenović, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Mostar Herz., VI.1925, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(MB)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – gemein; MTG – Rjeka, Podgorica; SB – Požarevac.

Müller (1926): SLO – valle d'Ospo; CRO – valle del Quietto (dalla foce fin Levade), Pisino.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Hrastovec, Lenart.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO - BH – SB - MTG

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA-Skopje, Katlanovo; Monospitovo swamp.

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: TUE

28. *B. (Philochthus) iricolor* Bedel, 1879

Guéorguiev (2011): CRO

Distribution: CRO

Chorotype: MED

29. *B. (Philochthus) lunulatum* (Geffroy in Fourcroy, 1785)

CROATIA

Petrovo Polje Dalm, 7.VIII.1922, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)
Hrvatska, Zagreb, Savica, V.1944, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Koljane D., 21.VI.1931, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂ imm.!(Dpa)
Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. S. Svirčev., 2 ♂♂ imm., 3 ♀♀ (2 imm.)!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Srbija, Niš, Kopajkošara, 18.VI.2001, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂ (with Laboulbeniales), 1 ♀!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Mostar Herz., V.1928, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂ imm.!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent, Travnik, Sarajevo, Višegrad; SB – Ak Palanka.

Müller (1926): SLO – nella vallata del Timavo suo. presso Ribnica e Mali Pristava, S. Servolo (presso il Monte Carso), Risano; CRO – Valle del Quietò (dalla foce fin Levade), Pisino, dint. Fiume.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Šalovci – Prekmurje.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO – BH – SB - MTG (Ulcinj)

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015) : NMA – more localities.

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities.

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: EUM

30. *B. (Philochthus) mannerheimii* C.R. Sahlberg, 1827

CROATIA

Prijevod, 1 ex.!(MB)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, Pl. Durmitor, Zminje jezero 1495 m, 4. VIII.1957, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex.!(Bon)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent, Sarajevo; MTG – Vlasulja.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *unicolor*): SLO - BH (B) - MTG (Vlasulja) - NMA

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – Majdanpek.

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – some bibliographic data.

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH – SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: SIE

Notes. Species new for Croatia.

- 31. *B. (Philochthus) neresheimeri* J. Müller, 1929)**
ssp. *neresheimeri* J. Müller, 1929)

Distribution: SLO

Chorotype: EUR

Notes. Vigna Taglianti (2004) mentions this species from Slovenia, but we don't know the original data.

subg. *Notaphus* Dejean, 1821

- 32. *B. (Notaphus) obliquum* Sturm, 1825**

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SB (Beograd)

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – Belgrade.

Distribution: SB

Chorotype: SIE

- 33. *B. (Notaphus) semipunctatum* (Donovan, 1806)**

CROATIA

Zagreb Cro, Sava, 2.VII.1942, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Zagreb Cro, Savica, 21.V.1943, leg. Svirčev, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Hrvatska, Zagreb, Savica, V.1944, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Slavonski brod, IV.1943, leg. S. Sviršev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Maksimir, 16.IV.1944, leg.S. Svir[čev, 3 ♂♂!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Srbija, Krusevac, IV.1934, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ♂♂!(Dpa, Bon)

Syrmium Zemun, 12.VIII.1942, leg. Ing. Osterman, 1 ♀!(MB)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *adustum*): BH – Brod, Derwent, Ključ, Sarajevo; SB – Milanovac, Golubac, Negotin, Požarevac, Semendria, Paraćin.

Müller (1926): refer of a citation of Padewieth (1907: 113) for CRO, that it would go checked.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Podkraj pri Hrastniku, Sava; Zagorje, Sava.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - CRO (Rijeka) - BH (B) - SB

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH - SB

Chorotype: ASE

34. *B. (Notaphus) varium* (Olivier, 1795)

CROATIA

Zagreb, Croatia, Sava, 2.VII.1942, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Zagreb Cro, Savica, 21.V.1943, leg. Svirčev, 2 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀!(MB, Bon)

N. Dalm., Env. Zemunik, 2.V.1919, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Env. De Zagreb, Savica-Alluvio, 24.VIII.1941, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Slavonski brod, IV.1943, leg. S. Svirčev, 7 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Sava, 2.VII.1952, leg. S. Svirčev, 4 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Zagreb, 20.VI.1942, leg. S. Svirčev, 4 ♂♂ (1 imm.), 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croazia, Isola di Cherso Ossero, 7.VII.71, Leg. De Martin 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Croazia, Isola di Cherso Ossero, 12.VII.73, Leg. De Martin 1 ♂ (CTVR)

SERBIA

Kušići Serb., Veliko Gradište, 2.VIII.1953, leg. Stančić, 22 ♂♂, 15 ♀♀ (many imm.)(MB)

Zaječar Serb, 10.VII.1934, leg. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Srem, Bežanija, 19.VII.1987, leg. M. Popović, 3 ex.!(Dpa)

Srem, Zemun, Novi Grad, 4.X. 1935 leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex. !(Dpa)

Srbija, Srem, Nova Pazova, 25.VIII.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Serb., Kruševac, env. d Obilićevo, 16.V.1935, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Dunav, Syrmium-Zemun, Kodric[?], 2.VIII.1941, 1 ♂ imm., 2 ♀♀!(MB)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Hc. Env. Mostar, Hum-M. blato, 2.VII.1930, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Hercegovina, Mostar, Mostarsko blato, VI.1927, leg.S. Sviršev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Plavnica Mont., 24.V.1947, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Reitter (1885): BH - “am Ufer der Bosna”.

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – gemein; CRO – Metkovic; MTG – Rjeka, Podgorica; SB – Negotin, Timokmündung, Kladovo, Paraćin, Straža.

Müller (1926): SLO - lago di Zirknitz (Carniola), Ospos; CRO – valle del Quietto inf., Porto di Fianona, dint. Fiume.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities
 Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – many localities
 Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – s. Ezerani.

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA
 Chorotype: PAL

subg. *Diplocampa* Bedel, 1896

35. *B. (Diplocampa) assimile* Gyllenhal, 1810

CROATIA

Dalmacija, Cetina, Vukovici, 1 ex.!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Kladovo Serb., 26.V.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Beograd, 15.VII.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srem, Zemun, Gardos, 1 ex leg. G. Nonveiller.!(Dpa)

Srbija, Zemun, 26.VI.1935, leg G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!Dpa)

Serbia, Požarevac, Rečica, 4.VI.1955, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, pl. Komovi 1800 m, 6.VII.1939, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – verbreitet, auch an der Meeresküste; CRO – Metkovic;
 MTG – Podgorica; SB – Požarevac.

Müller (1926): CRO – Valle del Quieto, Veglia.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO – BH - SB (Pozarevac) – MTG – NMA
 (Struga).

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA: many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – more localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: PAL

36. *B. (Diplocampa) fumigatum* (Duftschmid, 1812)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent, Utovo blato bei Gabela; CRO – Metkovic;
 SB – Negotin.

Müller (1926): CRO – foce del Narenta (presso Metkovic)

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - CRO (Da) - BH (Derventa, Hutovo blato) -
 SB (Negotin) – MTG (Ulcinj)

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – Negotin
Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - more localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH - SB – MTG - NMA
Chorotype: ASE

subg. *Semicampa* Netolitzky, 1910

37. *B. (Semicampa) gilvipes* Sturm, 1825

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SB - (Obedska bara)
Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – Obedska Bara.

Distribution: SB
Chorotype: EUR

38. *B. (Semicampa) schueppelii* Dejean, 1831

Netolitzky & Meyer (1938): SLO – Pettau
Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO (Sentilj)

Distribution: SLO
Chorotype: SIE

subg. *Trepanedoris* Netolitzky, 1918

39. *B. (Trepanedoris) doris* (Panzer, 1796)

SLOVENIA

SW Slovenia Ljubiana 25 km S Cerknisko lake, 14.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj,
1 ♂, 2 ♀♀ (CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent.

Müller (1926): SLO – Valle del Timavo sup. Pr. S. Canziano, Prevallo, lago
di Zirknitz.

Netolitzky & Meyer (1933b): SLO – St. Cauzian (Istrien); CRO - Karlstadt
[Karlovac]; SB – Morovič.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Cerknisko jezero (Ušiva loka, Goričica, Obrh,
Karlovica)

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – BH (Derventa)

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH - SB

Chorotype: SIE

subg. *Trepanes* Motschulsky, 1864

40. B. (*Trepanes*) *articulatum* (Panzer, 1796)

SLOVENIA

Slovenija, Lago di Cerknica q.500, 19-20/V/90, Leg. P. De Martin, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

NW Slovenia, Jezersko env. 20.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

CROATIA

Zagreb Cro, Savica, 21.V.1943, leg. Svirčev, 5 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Zagreb Croatia, Sava, 2.VII.1942, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Hrvatska, Zagreb, Savica, V.1944, leg. S. Svirčev, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 7 ♂♂, 10 ♀♀ (2 imm.)!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Solin, VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Maksimir, 16.IV.1944, leg. S. Svirčev, 3 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Istria, Pontpićan, 31.VII.2008, leg. P. Bonavita, 7 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀!(Bon)

Croatia, Isola di Cherso Beles Stagno Dolce, 8.VII.87, Leg. P. De Martin, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

SERBIA

Srbija, pl. Kopaonik, Svinjski Brod, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Beograd, Miljakovačka Šuma, 8. V.1992, 7 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Bor, pl. Veliki Krš, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Homoljske planine, Neresnica, 11.05.1997, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Radan Planina, Sokolovica, Bačije m 1000, 17.V.1989, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Beograd, Miljakovac, 8.V.1992, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Srem, Višnjicevo, 25.VII.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀ (imm.)!(Dpa)

Srbija, Beograd, Miljakovac, 29.V.1992, leg. D. Pavičević, 4 ♂♂!(Dpa, Bon)

Serbia, Pirot env. dol. riek., Jerme, na brehu, 28.IV.2002, leg. T. Jászay, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Zemun, 26.VI.1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Beograd, Miljakovac, 7.VI.1992, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Guča, selo Rti, Rčanska reka, 19.VII.2002, leg. D. Pavičević, 13 ♂♂, 10 ♀♀ (1 ♀ imm.)!(Dpa, Bon)

P. Bonavita and D. Pavićević: Catalogue of Bembidiina of former Yugoslavia 199

Srbija, Kruševac, Obilićevo-Rasina, Parunovac, 4.V.1934, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Serb., Kruševac, Env. Obilićevo, 21.III.1934, leg. Svirčev, 2 ♀♀ imm.!(Dpa)

Srbija, Sjenica, s. Usac, Ušaška pec., 30.VIII.2002-15.V.2003, leg. D. Pavićević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kruševac, IV.1934, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Serbia, Bujanovac, 28.VII.1957, leg. G. Nonveiller, 7 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Bosnia, Bjelašnica Mt., Korča 1200 m, VIII.1931, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

NORTH MACEDONIA

E Macedonia, Kocani env. at Dam-lake, 9-10-2007, Rudolf Kmeco leg., 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Reitter (1885): BH - "am Ufer der Bosna".

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – gemein, auch am Meeresstrande; MTG – Rjeka, Podgorica; SB – Požarevac, Negotin, Brza Palanka, Kladovo, Timokmündung, Surdulica, Stara planina.

Müller (1926): SLO – tutta la vallate di Recca d’Osopo fino alle Noghère, Roditti, Obrovo, Castelnuovo; CRO – Quietto pr. Levade, Pola.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Ćurčić et al. (2007 sub *elongatum*): SB – many localities.

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015) : NMA – many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: ASE

41. *B. (Trepanes) maculatum* Dejean, 1831

ssp. *maculatum* Dejean, 1831

ssp. *serbicum* Apfelbeck, 1902

CROATIA

Karaman, Solta, 1 ♀!(MB)

Croatia, Dalmatia, Solin, 24.VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀ (1 imm.)(MB)

SERBIA

Srem, Zemun, Gardoš, 10.V. 1984, leg. D. Pavićević, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srem, Bežanija, 23.IX. 1985, leg. M. Popović 1 ex!(Dpa)

Serbia, Požarevac, Rečica, 4.VI.1955, leg. G. Nonveiller, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Herzegovina, Mostar, 1.VIII.1927, leg. G. Nonveiller, 5 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *maculatum*): BH – dol. Hrasno; CRO – Dalmatien, Zara.

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *serbicum*): SB – in der alpinen Region der Stara-planina.

Müller (1926 sub *maculatum*): CRO – Salvo, Pola, isole di Veglia, Unie (Portolongo) e Arbe (Loparo).

Daniel K. (1903): BH – Utovo Blato.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *maculatum*): CRO (Adriatische Küste mit Inseln) - BH (Krasno) - NMA (Dojran)

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *serbicum*): Sb (Stara planina)

Ćurčić et al. (2007 both sub *maculatum* and *maculatum serbicum*: SB – Mt. Stara Planina

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015 sub *maculatum*): NMA – some bibliographic data.

Distribution: CRO - BH - SB - NMA

Chorotype: MED

Notes. *Bembidium serbicum* Apfelbeck, 1902 was described from Stara planina (SB) on a single specimen. Around this locality is diffused the ssp. *maculatus*. The status of the ssp. *serbicus* must be reviewed.

42. *B. (Trepanes) octomaculatum* (Goeze, 1777)

SLOVENIA

SW Slovenia, Ljubiana 25 km S, Cerknisko lake, 14.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

CROATIA

Split D., Žrnovica, 3.IX.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Imotski D., VII.1911, leg. Novak, 1 ♀ imm. !(Dpa)

SERBIA

Srbija, Beograd, VIII.2001, leg. A. Zatezalo, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Homoljske planine, Ceremošnjaja, nm 600m, 6.VI-27.VI.1998, leg. N. Ilić, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Srem, Nova Pazova, 25.VIII.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♀♀ (all imm.)(Dpa)

Zemun, Syrmium, leg. Kodric, 1 ♀ imm. !(MB)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Mostar Herz., 2.V.1926, leg. Svirčev, 5 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Bosna, Prolog planina, 3. VIII.1933, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

CROATIA

Croatia, Solin, 5.VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 13 ♂♂ (2 imm.), 23 ♀♀ (1 imm)!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Solin, VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 12 ♂♂ (2 imm.), 7 ♀♀ (1 imm.)!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Solin, VII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 10 ♂♂ (2 imm.), 4 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 25.VII.1925, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂ imm., 2 ♀♀ imm.!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 19.VIII.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 7 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 18.VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 19.VIII.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – gemein, auch am Meeresstrande; CRO – Knin, Spalato, Metkovich; MTG – Podgorica; SB – Negotin.

Müller (1926): CRO – Valle del Quieto inf, Pola, isola di Veglia.

Depoli (1930): CRO - Veglia.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - CRO (Istra, Da) – BH – MTG - NMA (Dojran)

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities.

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015) : NMA – many localities.

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: PAL

subg. *Talanes* Motschulsky, 1864

43. *B. (Talanes) aspericolle* (Germar, 1829)

Müller (1926): CRO – Zaule, Valle del Quieto.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO (Col) – CRO (MirnaTal)

Distribution: SLO - CRO

Chorotype: TUE

44. *B. (Talanes) subfasciatum* Chaudoir, 1850

CROATIA

Karaman Trau, 1 ♀!(MB)

Apfelbeck (1904): CRO – Traú-Karaman.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): CRO (Da)

Distribution: CRO

Chorotype: EME

subg. *Notaphemphanes* Netolitzky, 1920

45. *B. (Notaphemphanes) ephippium* (Marsham, 1802)

Apfelbeck (1904): MTG - Cattaro.

Netolitzky (1917a): CRO – Arbe, Starigrad, Zara; SLO – Capodistria.

Müller (1926): SLO – Capodistria; CRO – Is. Arbe.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO (Köper) - MTG (Kotor)

Guéorguiev (2011): CRO

Distribution: SLO – CRO - MTG

Chorotype: MED

subg. *Emphanes* Motschulsky, 1850

46. *B. (Emphanes) axillare* (Motschulsky, 1844)

ssp. *euxinum* Apfelbeck, 1904

SERBIA

Srbija, Zemun, 26.VI.1935, leg G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(MB)

Drovenik & Peks (1994): MTG (Ulcinj)

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – without precise locality (Matić, 1922)

ssp. *occiduum* Marggi & Huber, 2001

= *rivulare* Dejean, 1831

CROATIA

Istria, Val Quietto inf., 19.V.1929, leg. Pretner, 1 ♀!(MB)

Müller (1926 sub *minimum rivulare*): SLO – Capodistria; CRO – foce del Quietto, Arsa, isola Arbe.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *rivulare*): SLO (Köper) - CRO - BH (Gacko).

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB - MTG

Chorotype: CEM

47. *B. (Emphanes) azurescens* Dalla Torre, 1877

ssp. *azurescens* Dalla Torre, 1877

CROATIA

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. S.Svirčev, 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa Bon)

Croatia, Solin, VII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 19.VIII.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 25.VII.1925, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Sinj Dalm., 28.IV.1914, leg. Novak, 1 ♀!(MB)

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 20.VII.1943, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)3. X.

Croatia, Dalmatia, Solin, 24.VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Srbija, Beograd, Miljakovačka šuma, 20. IV. 1994, 2 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Srem, Zemun, Gardoš, 3. X. 1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex.!(Dpa)

Srbija, Zajecar, 13.VII.1934, leg. G. Nonveiller, 3 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Hercegovina, Mostar, IV.1927, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Müller (1926 sub *tenellum* Er.): SLO – lungo l'Isonzo a Tolmino, al Risano pr. Decani; CRO – Quieto pr. Levade.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - MTG (Ulcinj) - NMA

Guéorguiev (2011): BH

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA - r. Treska, s. Saraj,

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH – SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: TUE

Notes. Vigna Taglianti (2004) and Marggi et al. (2017) report this species from YU, which includes both Serbia and Montenegro. We know old data only from Montenegro, therefore perhaps this species is new for Serbia.

48. *B. (Emphanes) latiplaga* Chaudoir, 1850

ssp. *latiplaga* Chaudoir, 1850

NORTH MACEDONIA

Mavrovo, 27.V.1976, leg. Sama (Ner)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Čapljina an der Narenta; MTG – Rjeka, Podgorica; SB – Požarevac.

Schatzmayr (1939) – CRO – Metkovic

Drovenik & Peks (1994): BH (H) - SB (Pozarevac) - MTG

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Guéorguiev (2011): CRO

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - more localities

Distribution: CRO - BH - SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: TEM

49. *B. (Emphanes) minimum* (Fabricius, 1792)

SERBIA

Srbija, Zemun, 26.VI.1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♀♀!(MB, Bon)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, Durmitor, Sušičko jezero, m 1100, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♀!(MB)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent, Gacko; SB – Požarevac.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): BH (Derventa, Gacko) - SB (Pozarevac) - MTG (Ulcinj)

Drovenik & Peks (1999 sub *pusillum*): BH (Derventa, Gacko) – SB (Pozarevac) – MTG (Ulcinj)

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Distribution: BH - SB - MTG

Chorotype: CEM

50. *B. (Emphanes) normannum* Dejean, 1831

ssp. *apfelbecki* Müller-Motzfeld, 1986

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *normannum orientale*): CRO – Zara.

Müller-Motzfeld (1986b sub *apfelbecki*): NMA – Bistra.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *normannum apfelbecki*): CRO (Da)

Ćurčić et al. (2007 sub *normannum*): SB – many localities

ssp. *normannum* Dejean, 1831

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *normannum meridionale*): CRO – Agram [Zagreb],

Metkovich, Traú; BH – Mostar, Stolac, Domanović, Čapljina, Bilek, Neum; MTG – Rjeka, Podgorica; SB – Požarevac, Negotin, Timokmündung, Kladovo. Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *normannum meridionale*): CRO (Zagreb) – BH – SB – MTG
Čurčić et al. (2007 sub *normannum meridionale*): SB – many localities

Distribution: CRO – BH – SB – MTG – NMA

Chorotype: MED

Notes. The distribution, and perhaps the validity, of these subspecies needs to be reviewed; overlapping seems to result from the catalog of Marggi et al. (2017).

51. *B. (Emphanes) tenellum* Erichson, 1837

ssp. *tenellum* Erichson, 1837

CROATIA

Split D., Žrnovica, 3.IX.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Solin D., 14.VII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Split D., Žrnovica, 3.IX.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Solin D., 14.VII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)

SERBIA

Syrmium Zemun, Nova Pazova, 12.X.1942, leg. Ing. Osterman, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀!(MB, Bon)

Serbia, Veliko Gradište, Kutovo, 22.V.1951, leg. Stančić, 1 ♂!(MB)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Herz., Mostar, Bare, 1.VII.1927, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Env. Mostar Hc., Hum-M.blato, 16.IV.1926, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Env. de Mostar, Herc.-cent., 18.VII.1929, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Mostar Herz., V.1928, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Mostar Herz., Radobolje, 29.III.1923, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Montenegro, Durmitor Mt. Sušičko jezero 1100 m, 22.VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Virpazar-Sdr.J., IV.1934, leg P.Dabović, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Reitter (1885): BH – “am Ufer der Bosna”.

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – gemein, an Flussufern; CRO – Gravosa [Dubrovnik]; SB – Požarevac, Surdulica, Zaječar.

Müller (1926 sub *mocoticum* Kol.): CRO – Pola, Brioni.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG (Ulcinj) – NMA

(Matesevo)

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – more localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: SIE

subg, *Bembidion* Latreille, 1802

52. *B. (Bembidion) humerale* Sturm, 1825

ssp. *humerale* Sturm, 1825

Apfelbeck (1904): CRO – Umgebung von Agram.

Netolitzky & Meyer (1932b): CRO – Zagreb, Ludbreg, Dubrava, Fuzine; BH - Mokre poljane in Bosnien n.-w. von Glamoč.

Distribution: CRO - BH

Chorotype: SIE

53. *B. (Bembidion) quadrimaculatum* (Linnaeus, 1760)

ssp. *quadrimaculatum* (Linnaeus, 1760)

CROATIA

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 20.VII.1943, leg. S. Svirčev, 4 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Maksimir, 16.IV.1944, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Istria, Levada, f. Quieto, 6.III.1967, leg. Drioli, 1 ♂!(Bon)

Croatia, Istria, Potpićan, 31.VII.2008, leg. Bonavita, 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Bon)

Croatia, Isola di Cherso Ossero, 12.VII.73, Leg. P. De Martin 1 ♂ (CTVR)

SERBIA

Srbija, Srem, Višnjicevo, 25.VII.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Požezeno, V. Gradište Serb., 10.VI.1956, leg. Stančić, 1 ♀!(MB)

Srbija, Osipaonica, 4 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Srem, Zemun, Novi Grad, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srem, Zemun, Bežanijska Kosa, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Srem, Zemun, 20.IV.1937, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Serbia, Srem, Fruška Gora, 9.VI.1957, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Serbia, Bujanovac, 28.VII.1957, leg. G. Nonveiller, 3 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Hercegovina, Mostar, IV.1927, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, Pj Durmitor, Zabljak 1500m, 2 ex!(Dpa)

Reitter (1885 sub *quadriguttatum* Fbr.): BH - "am Ufer der Bosna".

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – verbreitet; CRO – Knin; SB – Požarevac, Semendria, Negotin.

Müller (1926): SLO - Tolmino, Volzana (Volče), Castelnovo, Erpelle, Roditti, Nevoso, Hermsburg; CRO – Pisino, Pola, dint. Fiume.

Müller (1926 sub *quadriguttatum* Ol.): CRO – Pola, valle del Quieto inf., dint. Fiume, Vrata pr. Fužine.

Netolitzky & Meyer (1932d sub *quadriguttatum* F.): SLO – Laibach, Čatež, Marburg [Maribor]; CRO – Vinkovci, Agram, Vrata; SB – Belgrad, Paračin, Ruma; BH – Pale, Foča a. Drina, Bosnatal, Salona, Derwent, Sarajevo, Višegrad, Brčka a. Save, Bilek, Metkovič.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO – BH - SB

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – more localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: PAL

54. *B. (Bembidion) quadripustulatum* Audinet-Serville, 1821
ssp. *quadripustulatum* Audinet-Serville, 1821

CROATIA

Zagreb Cro, Savica, 21.V.1943, leg. Svirčev, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Solin D., 14.VII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 5 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Solin, 5.VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 25.VII.1925, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂ imm., 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 19.VIII.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Srbija, Beograd, Miljakovac, 8.V.1992, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Env. Mostar, Goranci-Hc., IV.1928, leg. S. Svirčev, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Hercegovina, Mostar, IV.1927, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *quadriguttatum* Fabr.): BH – Dervent, Sarajevo, Višegrad, Bilek, Dračevo bei Metkovich; MTG – Rjeka; SB – Paraćin.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG – NMA (Skopje)

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Guéorguiev (2011): SB Kosovo, Montes Koprivnik

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - Jugoslawien Macedonien leg. F. Hieke” / “Skopje Vardar-Ufer

Distribution: SLO - CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: CEM

subg. *Hirmoplataphus* Netolitzky, 1943

55. *B. (Hirmoplataphus) friebi* Netolitzky, 1914

SLOVENIA

Styria mer., Brezice, 1934, leg. Kodric, 1 ♂!(MB)

SLO, Krško, 10.VIII.2004, leg. A. Casale, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Cas, Bon)

Hrastnik, 10.5.1990, Podkraj SL, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Podkraj pri Hrastniku, Sava

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO (Sevniva)

Guéorguiev (2011): CRO

Distribution: SLO – CRO

Chorotype: SEU (ALPE)

subg. *Microserrullula* Netolitzky, 1921

56. *B. (Microserrullula) quadricolle* (Motschulsky, 1844)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *inserticeps* Chd.): SB – Požarevac.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SB (Pozarevac).

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – Požarevac.

Guéorguiev (2011): BH

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Distribution: SLO - BH – SB - NMA

Chorotype: TUE

Notes. Vigna Taglianti (2004) mentions its presence in SLO; we don't

know the original data.

subg. *Odontium* LeConte, 1847

57. *B. (Odontium) foraminosum* Sturm, 1825

CROATIA

Zagreb, Croatia, Sava, 2.VII.1942, leg. Svirčev, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Zagreb, Croatia, Sava, 2.VII.1942, leg. Svirčev, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Zagreb, Sava, 24.VI.1942, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Env. De Zagreb, Savica-Alluvio, 24.VIII.1941, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Reitter (1885): BH - "am Ufer der Bosna".

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent, Sarajevo, Višegrad.

Netolitzky & Saint-Claire Deville (1913): SB – Čačak; BH – Ilidze; Sarajevo; Visegrad; Dervent; Bosnaufer.

Drovenik (1994): SLO - Podkraj pri Hrastniku, Sava

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – BH (B) – SB - NMA

Drovenik & Peks (1999): SLO – CRO (Slavonski Brod) - BH (B) – SB - NMA

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – citations without locality (Hieke & Wrase, 1988; Drovenik & Peks, 1999)

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - Skopje: s. Orešani

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – Skopje: s. Orešani

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH - SB - NMA

Chorotype: EUR

58. *B. (Odontium) striatum* (Fabricius, 1792)

SERBIA

Serb. Kusići, V. Gradište, 2.VIII.1954, leg. Stančić, 1 ♂!(MB)

MONTENEGRO

Plavnica Mont., 24.V.1947, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Čaplina a. d. Narenta; MTG – Rjeka; SB – Požarevac.

Netolitzky (1918a): (Apfelbeck, 1904: BH – Narenta; MTG – Rjeka; SB – Požarevac).

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – BH (B) – SB - MTG

Drovenik & Peks (1999): SLO – CRO (Slavonski Brod) - BH (B) – SB - MTG

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities.

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - Skopje: Zoološka Gradina; Skopje.
Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – more localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO - BH – SB – MTG - NMA
Chorotype: SIE

subg. *Bracteon* Bedel, 1879

59. *B. (Bracteon) argenteolum* Ahrens, 1812

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO
Guéorguiev (2011): CRO

Distribution: SLO - CRO
Chorotype: SIE

60. *B. (Bracteon) litorale* (Olivier, 1790)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Bosn. Or., Uvaç, leg. Hensch, 1 ♀!(MB)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, Durmitor pl., Tepca m 500, 24.VI.1987, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Višegrad.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – BH (B) – MTG

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - more localities

Distribution: SLO – BH – SB - MTG - NMA
Chorotype: SIE

? ***B. (Bracteon) velox* (Linnaeus, 1760)**

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities

Notes. Ćurčić et al. (2007) report data from Csiki (1946) and Petrik (1958) referring to another species (*B. lampros*) or to other states (Romania and Hungary) (Neri, pers. comm.). Besides, because no other authors mention this species for Balkans, it may be possible that this species was actually confused with *O. foraminosum* or *O. litorale*.

subg. *Chlorodium* Motschulsky, 1864

61. *B. (Chlorodium) pygmaeum* (Fabricius, 1792)

[without target], 1 ♂!(MB)

SERBIA

V. Gradiste, 20.V.1957, leg. Stančić, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(MB, Bon)

Netolitzky (1923): SLO – Tolmein u. Podgora; CRO – Fiume, Varasdin; BH – Sarajevo, Jablanica, Ilidže, Konjica, Igbar; SB – Požarevac.

Müller (1926): SLO – Sonzia, Tolmino.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO - BH (H, Tjentiste) - SB (Pec) – NMA (Matka).

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - more localities

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH - SB - NMA

Chorotype: EUR

62. *B. (Chlorodium) splendidum* Sturm, 1825

ssp. *pincum* De Monte, 1957

CROATIA

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 3 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Zagreb, Sava, 24.VI.1942, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Env. de Zagreb, Alluvio Save, 11.V.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 20.VII.1943, leg. S. Svirčev, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

SERBIA

V. Gradiste, 20.V.1957, leg. Stančić, 9 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀!(MB, Bon)

19.V.1957, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(MB)

Serbia, Nis – Katun, 23.V.1981, Leg. Sama, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀ (CTVR)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Gevgelija Mace, 28.V.1957, leg. Nonveiller, 7 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Mac. Gevgelija, 28.V.1957, leg. Stojković, 5 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent, Čapljina a. d. Narenta; SB – Požarevac.

Netolitzky & Meyer (1936a): SLO – Laibach, Sevnica, Brezice; CRO – Agram, Metkovic, Castelnuoco [Kastel Novi]; BH – Brčka, Dervent; SB – Serbia.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *splendidum*): SLO – BH – SB - NMA

Ćurčić et al. (2007 sub *splendidum*): SB – many localities

Guéorguiev (2011): CRO

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015 sub *splendidum splendidum*): NMA - more localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB - NMA

Chorotype: EEU

subg. *Metallina* Motschulsky, 1850

63. B. (*Metallina*) *lampros* (Herbst, 1784)

SLOVENIA

Slov. Železniki, 24.VI.1933, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Slov. Pungert, 17.V.1916, leg. Pretner, 1 ♂ imm., 1 ♀!(Dpa)

CROATIA

Croatia, Zagreb, Maksimir, 16.IV.1944, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Sleme Bizek, Zagreb. Gora, 2.VII.1939, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Velebit sett., Siča 1300 m, 13.VI.1996, leg. G. Colombetta, 2 ♂♂!(Col)

SERBIA

Srbija, Donja Šatornja, 31.05.1998, leg. D. Pavičević (2 ex)!(Dpa)

Srbija, Suva Planina, Škrveno m 1550, 18.V.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Radan Planina, Sokolovica, Bačije m 1000, 17.V.1989, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kosovo, Šar planina, Čop m 1500, 28.VII.1995, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Suva planina, Provalija, nm 1500m, 4.V.2001, leg. M. Stevanović, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Suva planina, Škrveno, Bela Stena, 15.V-17.VI.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Suva planina, Ždrebica, nm 1300 m, 8.VI.2000, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Jelavci, nm 480 m, 18.VI.2001, leg. B. Blesić, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Syrmium Zemun, 8.VI.1942, leg. Ing. Osterman, 1 ♂!(MB)

Serb., Kosmovac, Suva Planina, 2.V.1953, leg. Stančić, 1 ♂!(MB)

Serb. Kopaonik m 1700, 2.VIII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀ (di cui 1 imm.)!(Dpa, Bon)

Serb. Kopaonik, fagetum, 3.VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂ imm.!(Dpa)

Srbija Šar pl., Stojkova kuća, nm 1700 m, 19.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 3

♂♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Zemun, 29IV.1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 3 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, pl. Bukulja, 19.VI.1955, leg. G. Nonveiller, 8 mm, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, pl. Kablar 280 m, 1.X.1995, leg. B. Blesić, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Javor pl., Šitkovo, 12.V.2003, leg. D. Pavičević, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Pirot, Kopren 1500 m, 5.IX.1955, leg. Stančić, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(MB)

Srbija, Srem, Fruška Gora, 9.VI.1957, leg. G. Nonveiller, 5 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Serbia: Nis region, Suva Planina, 640 m, Babicka Gora, Kosuta, 5.vii.2006, Leg. J. Cooter, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Kopaonik Serb. 1800m, 1.IX 1959, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Kopaonik Serb., m 1700, 1.IX.1959, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂ (immaturi)!(Dpa)

Šar planina Durlov potok, m 1800, 25.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, pl Durmitor, Veliki Stuoč 2000m, 5.VIII.1958, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl Durmitor, Mlinski potok, 1500m, 27. VI. 1958, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl Durmitor, Zabljak 1500m, 27.VI.1958, leg. G. Nonveiller. 1 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl Durmitor, Zabljak 1450m, 25.VI.1958, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex!(MB)

Crna Gora, pl Durmitor, Crno jezero 1450m, 25.VI. 1958, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ex!(MB, Bon)

Crna Gora, planina Prokletije Bukumirsko jezero, 12.VII. 1934, leg. P. Dabović 1 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, Šavnik, pl. Durmitor, Komarnica, 20.VIII.1995, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, Durmitor, Žabljak, Crno Jezero m 1450, 23.VI.1987, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, Pljevlja, Kaluderovići, Klisura Sutjeske, 21.VIII.1995, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♀!Dpa)

Crna Gora, Durmitor, Grabovica, 19.VIII.1995, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, Durmitor, Pitomine, 2.VII.1958, leg G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Mont., Durmitor, Crno jezero, 27.VI.1958, leg. Janković, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Mont., Durmitor, Crno jezero, 3.VII.1958, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Mont., Durmitor, Mali Štulac m 1700, 30.VI.1958, leg. Stoiković, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Mont., Durmitor, Valovito jezero, 4.VII.1980, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Mont., Durmitor, Podgora, 6.VII.1958, leg. Stojković, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Mont., Durmitor, Podgora, 6.VII.1958, leg. Stančić, 1 ♀!(MB)

Mont., Durmitor, Veliki Štulac, 30.VI.1958, leg. G. Nonveiller, 5 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Mont., Durmitor, Veliki Štulac m 2000, 23.VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Mont., Durmitor, Žabljak m 1450, 4.VII.1958, leg. Stojković, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl. Komovi 1800 m, 5.VII.1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Crna Gora, pl. Komovi 1800 m, 6.VII.1939, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Mont., Komovi Mt. 1500 m, 8.VII.1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Mont., Durmitor Mt. Žabljak 1450 m, 12.VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Vilinaš pl. Čvrtnica, 16.VII.1927, leg. Svirčev, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Bosna, Mt. Bjelašnica 1500m, 2.VII.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller 1 ex!(Dpa)

Bosna, Teslic, Čečava, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Domanovići Herz., 14.XI.1916, leg. Novak, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Bosna, Prolog planina, 3. VIII.1933, leg G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Bosna, Mlinište, 9.VIII.1935, leg G. Nonveiller, 3 ♀♀ (2 ♀♀ imm.)(Dpa)

Herz., Domanovići, 14.XI.1916, leg. Novak, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Bos., Prenj plan., Boračko jezero, 30.VI.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Bosna, pl. Bjelašnica, 18.VII.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Bosna, Bjelašnika Mt., Korča 1200 m, VIII.1931, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Bosna, Teslič-Čečevo, V.1928, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Bosna, Bjelašnica Mt., Korča, Lanište 1200 m, 2.VII.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Prolog. Bos., VII.1912, leg. Novak, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Zavala Herz., 23.V.1951, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Pločna-Velež pl., Fagus Rg., 1500 m, 30.VI.1932, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Makedonija, Pl. Bistra, Galičnik 1650m, 12. VI.1983, leg. D. Pavićević, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Mac., Šar planina, Popova Šapka, 1.VI.1957, leg. Stojković, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Macedonia, Šar pl., Piribeg m 2100, 26.VII.1975, leg. D. Pavićević, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Reitter (1885): BH - "am Ufer der Bosna".

Apfelbeck (1904: the localities are relative to *lampros* and *properans*, without distinction between these two species): BH – gemein, auch in der alpinen Region; CRO – Metkovic; MTG – Cetinje, Sutorman, Durmitor; SB – Bela Palanka, Suva planina, Kladovo, Surdulica, Stara planina, Mućanj plan.

Müller (1926): SLO - S. Lucia, M. Nero di Tolmino, Porezen, Lipizza, Roditti, Aidussina, M. Taiano; CRO – Lupolano, M. Maggiore, Viševica, Zlobin, Obruč, Valle Kostajnovica, Grohovo.

Depoli (1930): SLO - Nevoso (Svinscjachi); CRO – M. Maggiore (in vetta sotto i sassi), M. Aquila (bosco), gruppo dell'Obruč, Lič, Viševica (praterie).

Drovenik (1994): SLO – many localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *splendidum*): SLO – CRO - BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Čurčić & Stanković (2011): SB – Valjevac

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: PAL

64. *B. (Metallina) properans* (Stephens, 1828)

9 [without other target], 1 ♀!(MB)

SLOVENIA

SLO, Zalog, Kamnik, 28.III.1996, leg. G. Colombetta, 1 ♂!(Col)

Slovenija, Lago di Cerknica q.500, 19-20/V/90, Leg. P. De Martin, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

NW Slovenia, Jezerki env., 20.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

CROATIA

Sinj Dalm., 28.IV.1914, leg. Novak, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Ljeskovac Cro, 11.V.1933, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Cr. Env. De Zagreb, Markuševac, pod Sljemenom, 14.IV.1946, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Cro., Križevac, VI.1900, leg. Novak, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Srem, Zemun, Bežanijska kosa, 5.VI.1985, leg. M. Popovič, 2 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Srem, Zemun, Novi Grad, 3. X.1935, letg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Stara planina, Zarkova Cuka 1600m, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Požega, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Syrmium Zemun, 22.V.1942, leg. Ing. Osterman, 1 ♀!(MB)

Syrmium Zemun, 4.VI.1942, leg. Ing. Osterman, 1 ♀!(MB)

Syrmium Zemun, 8.V.1942, leg. Ing. Osterman, 1 ♀!(MB)

Syrmium Zemun, 25.V.1942, leg. Ing. Osterman, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(MB)

Serb. Kragujevac, Grošnica, 4.IV.1989, leg. Blesić, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

V. Gradiste, 20.V.1957, leg. Stančić, 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(MB)

Srbija, Krusevac, IV.1934, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kruševac, Obilićevo, VII.1934, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kosovo, Djakovica Metohija, 24.V.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Herc. Avtovac, 26.V.1951, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Herc. Zavala, 23.V.1951, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Mostar Herz., V.1929, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Bos., Prenj plan., Boračko jezero, 30.VI.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Bosna, pl. Bjelasnica, 18.VII.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Bosna, Bjelašnica Mt., Korča 1200 m, VIII.1931, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Bosna, Rupovo Brdo, Vlasenica, 10.IV.1956, leg. Stančić, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(MB)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Mac. Gostivar, Polog, 3.VI.1957, leg. Uzunov, 1 ♀!(MB)

Apfelbeck (1904: the localities are relative to *lampros* and *properans*, without distinction between these two species): BH – gemein, auch in der alpinen Region; CRO – Metkovic; MTG – Cetinje, Sutorman, Durmitor; SB – Bela Palanka, Suva planina, Kladovo, Surdulica, Stara planina, Mućanj plan.

Müller (1926): SLO – Comeno, Senosecchia, Matteredia; CRO – Salvore, Pola.

Depoli (1930): CRO - Lisina (presso il rifugio), bosco di faggi tra Sappiane e Bergud, Clana (bosco), Skrljevo (rive del laghetto), Zlobin, Lič (campo), Vrata, Viševica (praterie), Grohovo, Breggi, Sgorničko, altopiano a S del Mdvedjak.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO - BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: PAL

subg. *Hydrium* LeConte, 1847

65. *B. (Hydrium) laticolle* (Duftschmid, 1812)

SERBIA

Srbija, Zemun, 26.VI.1935, leg G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Syrmium Zemun, 12.VIII.1942, leg. Kodric, 1 ♀!(MB)

Apfelbeck (1904): SB – Požarevac.

Netolitzky (1917b): CRO – Agram, Ludbreg bei Varasdin, Osijek und Budaševo bei Sisak, Rajevoselo und Račinovci (Umgebung von Vinkovci,

Slavonien); BH - Saveufer bei Šamac; SB – Klenak a. Save in Syrmien und O-Becse a. Theiß, (Apfelbeck, 1904: Požarevac), Serbien (coll. Heyden).

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – SB

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – Dubravica, Požarevac.

Guéorguiev (2011): CRO – ‘First record for Croatia’(sic!)

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH - SB - MTG

Chorotype: EUR

subg. *Plataphus* Motschulsky, 1864

66. *B. (Plataphus) prasinum* (Duftschmid, 1812)

CROATIA

Zagreb Sava, 20.VI.1942, leg. S. Svirčev, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Hercegovina, Diva Grabovica, VI.1930, leg. Svirčev, 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Netolitzky (1913a): SLO – Savica (Save-Ursprung), Wochein [Bohinj], Reichenburg (Saveufer), Steinbrück; CRO – Agram [Zagreb], Papukgebirge.

Müller (1926): SLO – cascata della Savizza

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Pod Lubnikom, Selska Sora

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO

Neri & Toledano (2021): MTG

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH - MTG

Chorotype: SIE

subg. *Princidium* Motschulsky, 1864

67. *B. (Princidium) punctulatum* Drapiez, 1820

ssp. *punctulatum* Drapiez, 1820

SLOVENIA

SLO, Krško, 10.VIII.2004, leg. A. Casale, 4 ♀♀!(Ca)

CROATIA

Dragovič, Vrlika D., IX.1901, leg. Novak, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Savica, 24.VIII.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 8 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Zagreb, Sava, 24.VI.1942, leg. S. Svirčev, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Sava, 2.VII.1942, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Imotski D., VII.1905, leg. Novak, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Velik, Gradište, Kušići, 2.VIII.1954, leg. Stančić, 2 ♂♂!(MB)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Crno jezero 1480 m, 3.VII 1958, leg. G. Nonveiller, 5 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Crno jezero 1425 m, 4.VIII 1958, leg. G. Nonveiller, 11 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Reitter (1885): BH - "am Ufer der Bosna".

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – gemein; CRO – Knin, Metkovic; MTG – Rjeka; SB – Milanovac, Golubac, Negotin, Suva plan.

Müller (1926): SLO – „al torrente Recca tra Ospos e Noghera“, Risano; CRO – „dint. Fiume“.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO (Da) – BH – SB – MTG – NMA (Dojran)

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities.

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015) : NMA – many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: TEM

? *B. (?Principidium) idriae* Meschnigg, 1934

Species described from Idrija (Slovenia), but never collected again. Species of doubt validity (Vigna Taglianti, 1993), possibly referring to subg. *Principidium*, perhaps *punctulatum* (Neri et al., 2011).

subg. *Testedium* Motschulsky, 1864

68. *B. (Testedium) bipunctatum* (Linnaeus, 1760)

ssp. *bipunctatum* (Linnaeus, 1760)

= ssp. *nivale* (Dejean, 1831)

= ssp. *pyritosum* (P. Rossi, 1792)

SLOVENIA

Triglav Slov., Trigavska jezera, 2.VI.1933, leg. Nonveiller, 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

SERBIA

Srbija, Sar planina, Durlov potok, nm 1500m, 20.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Sar planina, Gornje jezero??, 2.VII., leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Hercegovina, Plasa planina, Donja Grabovica, 5.VIII.1927, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Bosna, pl. Bjelasnica, 18.VII.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Čvrstica Mt., Hrc., Vilinac m 1900, VII.1927, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Tepca 500 m, 12.07.1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Todorov do 1900m, 25.VI.1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Sedlo 1900m, 25.VI, 1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 16 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Meded 1700m, 29. VI.1985,leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ex!(MB)

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Velika Karlica, 1950m 7.07.1985, leg. D. Pavičević, , 2 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Velika Karlica, 2000m, 20. VII 1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 8 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, Durmitor, Todorov do, nm 1900m, 26.VI.1987, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Durmitor Mont., Jakšića katuni m 1800, 16.VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl. Komovi 2300 m, 6.VII.1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 5 ♂♂, 10 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Crna Gora, pl. Komovi 1800 m, 6.VII.1939, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Montenegro, Durmitor Mt. Jakšića katuni 1700 m, 16.VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Montenegro, Durmitor Mt. Savin Kuk 1900 m, 15.VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀!(Dpa)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Šar pl., Mac., 17.VI.1950, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – in der alpinen Region der Hochgebirge überall häufig an Schneerändern; MTG – Durmitor.

Müller (1926 sub *nivale* Heer): SLO – Mangart; M. Nero di Piedicolle, M. Nero di Tolmino.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *nivale* and *pyritosum*): SLO – BH – MTG – NMA
(alpin, Korab)

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015) : NMA – many localities.

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – many localities

Distribution: SLO – BH – SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: SIE

69. *B. (Testedium) quadrifossulatum* Schaum, 1862

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – Gevgelija, Bogdanci, Karabalijska

Distribution: MA

Chorotype: EME

70. *B. (Testedium) trebinjense* Apfelbeck, 1899

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Herzegovina, Trebinje, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Trebinje.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): BH (H. Trebinje)

Distribution: BH

Chorotype: SEU (BALK)

subg. *Testediolum* Ganglbauer, 1891

71. *B. (Testediolum) glaciale* Heer, 1837

= *intractabile* De Monte, 1946

SLOVENIA

Grintovec-Savin, Alpe-Drav banov, 16.VI.1935, leg. Pretner, 1 ♀!(MB)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Medjed 1700 m, 29.VI 1985, leg. D. Pavićević, 2
ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Mont., Durmitor, Veliki Štulac, 6.VII.1958, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa,
Bon)

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Medjed m 1700, 18.VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Montenegro, Durmitor Mt. Savin Kuk 1900 m, 15.VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 6 ♂♂, 10 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Vran planina, Volujak, Vlasulja bei Čemerno; MTG – Volujak, Durmitor.

Müller (1926 sub *pyren. Glaciale*): SLO - Tricorno, Val Trenta, M. Canin, M. Nero di Caporetto.

Meyer (1950) – SLO – Petzen.

Vysoký (1986): BH – Bosnia.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Raduha, Kamniško-Savinjske Alpe.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *glaciale glaciale* and *glaciale intractabile*): SLO (Julische Alpen, Karawanken, Steiner Alpen) - BH(H) - MTG

Distribution: SLO - BH – ?SB – MTG

Chorotype: CEU

72. *B. (Testediolum) julianum* De Monte, 1943

SLOVENIA

Slovenia, Triglav [Muilwjik], (All)

Slovenia, M.te Canin, mt. 2000, Bovec, 14.07.2002, Leg. A. Degiovanni, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Kokrško sedlo, Kamniško-Savinjske Alpe.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO (Julische Alpen, Karawanken, Steiner Alpen)

Distribution: SLO

Chorotype: SEU (ALPE)

73. *B. (Testediolum) magellense* Schaubberger, 1922

ssp. *alpicola* (Jeannel, 1941)

Distribution: SLO

Chorotype: SEU (ALAP)

Notes. Vigna Taglianti (2004) mentions this species from Slovenia, but we don't know the original data.

subg. *Nepha* Motschulsky, 1864

74. *B. (Nepha) callosum* Küster, 1847ssp. *callosus* Küster, 1847

Drovenik & Peks (1994): MTG (Ulcinj)

Bonavita & Vigna (2010): MTG – Ulcinj; Petrovac

Distribution: MTG

Chorotype: MED

75. *B. (Nepha) caucasicum* (Motschulsky, 1844)

9, 1 ♂!(MB)

SERBIA

Srbija, Šar planina, Durlov potok, m 1500, 20.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Šar planina, Durlov potok, nm 1500m, 20.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Šar planina, Durlov potok, nm 1700 m, 20.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kosovo, Šar planina, Dolovi, 2100 m, 24.VI.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Hercegovina, Plasa planina, Donja Grabovica, 5.VIII.1997, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Hercegovina, Plasa planina, Donja Grabovica, 5.VIII.1927, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Bosnia, Bjelasnica, F. Blühweiss, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, pl. Komovi 2300 m, 6.VII.1939, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Mac., Šar planina, Popova Šapka, 1900 m, 1.VI.1957, leg. Stojković, 1 ♂!(MB)

Salakovi Ezera, Mt. Jakupica m 2260, 15.VII.1999, leg. Biology students' research '99, 1 ♂!(MB)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *substriatum* Chaud.): BH – Bjelašnica planina bei Sarajevo, Vran planina bei Prozor, Prenj planina, Baba plan. Bei Bilek.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): BH - MA

Bonavita & Vigna (2010): many localities of SB – BH – MTG - NMA

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – many localities

Distribution: BH - SB - MTG – NMA

Chorotype: TUE

76. *B. (Nepha) genei* Küster, 1847

ssp. *illigeri* Netolitzky, 1914

SLOVENIA

Slovenia, Capodistria [=Koper], Pozza Valle di Stagnone, 22.V.2011, leg. Colombetta, 1 ♂!(Col)

CROATIA

Croatia, Isola di Cherso Beles Stagno Dolce, 8.VII.87, Leg. P. De Martin, 8 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀ (CTVR)

Müller (1926): SLO – Roditti; CRO – Pisino, Fiume, Cherso, Arbe.

Depoli (1930): CRO – Sappiane (in riva al ruscello nel polje).

Netolitzky & Meyer (1937 sub *Illigeri* Net.): SLO – Aidussina, Bigliana nel Coglio, Pettau, Rohitsch, Podčetrtek, Maribor, Kalobje, Lichtenwald und S. Paul, Bled-Veldes, Radmannsdorf, Decani-Risano, Erpelle, Nigrignano; CRO – Fiume-Rečinalat, Vranja und Is. Brioni, Pisino und Cherso, Levade-Quieto, Zagreb, Novi Prim, Arbe, Sušak b. Fiume, Vinkovce, Slav. Brod.

Drovenik (1994 sub *illigeri*): SLO – Šalovci, Prekmurje.

Drovenik & Peks (1999 sub *tetragrammum illigeri*): SLO - CRO

Bonavita & Vigna (2010): many localities of SLO and CRO; SB: Slavonia, Ruma

Distribution: SLO - CRO - SB

Chorotype: EUM

77. *B. (Nepha) retipenne* J. Müller, 1918

Apfelbeck (1904), Drovenik & Peks (1994) and Ćurčić et al. (2007) reported, sub *menetriesii*, a locality: SB – Stara planina. Seeing as how *menetriesii* doesn't occur in the Balkan, the data have to refer to this species or *rufimacula*.

Bonavita & Vigna (2010): SB – Mldzor; NMA - Vlachi Pirin

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - Kožuf, Boshava River, 700m, near Konopishte Village

Distribution: SB – NMA
 Chorotype: TUM (BAN)

78. *B. (Nepha) rufimacula* J. Müller, 1918

EX-YUGOSLAVIA

Balkan, 1 ♀!(NHMW-V)

Yugoslavia, passo di Vorila!(MSTV).

NORTH MACEDONIA

Mac., Kresnicko Def., leg. Mař. & Táb., 2 ♂♂!(MSNM-Sc); Macedonia, Pelister, Kazani env. 1000 m, 18-19.VII.1997, leg. P. Moravec, 1 ♂!(Reb).

Apfelbeck (1904), Drovenik & Peks (1994) and Ćurčić et al. (2007) reported, sub *menetriesii*, a locality: SB – Stara planina. Seeing as how *menetriesii* doesn't occur in the Balkan, the data have to refer to this species or to *retipenne*.

Bonavita & Vigna (2010): NMA – some localities.

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – more localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – Bistrica

Distribution: ?SB - NMA

Chorotype: TUM (BAN)

79. *B. (Nepha) vseteckai* Mařan, 1936

ssp. *dissimile* J. Müller, 1943

CROATIA

Petrovo Polje, Drniř-Dalm., V.1923, leg. S. Svirĉev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Kroatien, Velebit, Baske Ostarije, 04.07.2014, Lg. Dostal, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

SERBIA

Srbija, Guĉa, selo Rti, Rĉanska reka, 19.VII.2002, leg. D. Paviĉeviĉ, 2 ♂♂ (Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Zlatibor, kod Pipalske, peĉine, 10.VIII.2002, leg. D. Paviĉeviĉ, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Niř, Cerje, 500 m, 12.VI.2000, leg. M. Popoviĉ, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Niř, Kopajkořara, 18.VI.2001, leg. M. Popoviĉ, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, pl. Avala, 2.VI.1990, leg. M. Popoviĉ, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERCEGOVINA

Buna-Blagaĵ H, Env. Mostar, 30.VI.1932, leg. S. Svirĉev, 1 ♂ imm.!(Dpa)

Mostar Herz., V.1928, leg. Svirčev, 1m imm., 3 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, Kotor, 19.VIII.1957, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

YU Crna Gora, Skadarsko I., Virpazar env., 7.vii.2002, P. Bulirsch lgt., 1 ♂
(CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *Genei* Küster): BH – gemein; MTG – Cattaro, Rjeka, Cetinje, Sutorman Pass, Durmitorgebiet; SB – Kladovo, Stara plan.

Netolitzky & Meyer (1937 sub *Illigeri* Net.): CRO – Vrlika, Salona, Cirkvenica; SB - Kosore; BH – Mostar, Mostarsko blato, Prenj plan., Brčka und Rocatica, Čelič und Bosn. Brod, Teslić, Majeveca plan; MTG – Zelenika, Canale und Krivosije, Grgaje.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *genei illigeri*): BH – SB – MTG - NMA (Ovce pole)

Drovenik & Peks (1999 sub *tetragrammum illigeri*): BH – SB – MTG - NMA (Ovce pole)

Čurčić et al. (2007 sub *illigeri*): SB – many localities

Bonavita & Vigna (2010): many localities of CRO – SB – BH – MTG

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – more localities

Distribution: CRO - BH - SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: EME

subg. *Bembidionetolitzkya* E. Strand, 1929

80. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) ascendens* K. Daniel, 1902

= *axillare* K. Daniel, 1902

SLOVENIA

Slov., Kranj, Kokra, 17.VI.1940, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Daniel K. (1902 sub *fasciolatum ascendens* Dan.): BH – Tatra, Sarajewo (Zeljeznica, Pracá, Olovo, Kiseljak), Vlasenica und Džile; (sub *fasciolatum axillare* Dan.): Zeljeznia Fluss bei Sarajewo.

Müller (1926 sub *fasciolatum ascendens* Dan.): SLO – Plezzo, Tolmino, Volzana (Volče), Salcano, Aidussina (valle del Vipacco), Loke e Vreme al Timavo sup., Bochinia (alla sorgente della Savizza); CRO – Lupolano probabilmente lungo qualche affluente dell'Arsa).

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Radovljica, Sava; pod Lubnikom, Selška Sora.
 Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - CRO (Istra. Lupoglav) - BH (B)

Distribution: SLO – CRO - BH
 Chorotype: CEU

81. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) brunoi* (Bonavita, 2001)

CROATIA

Zagreb Sava, 20.VI.1942, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(MB)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Hercegovina, Diva Grabovica, VI.1930, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀ (paratypes)!(Dpa, Bon)

Hercegovina, Diva Grabovica, VI.1930, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Bonavita (2001): BH - Diva Grabovica

Guéorguiev (2011): MTG

Distribution: CRO – BH – MTG

Chorotype: SEU (BALK)

Notes. Species new for Croatia.

82. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) bugnioni* K. Daniel, 1902

Bonavita & Vigna (1993): SLO – S. Lucia di Tol. (Slap), Gorenje (Konc).

Müller (1926): CRO – Vragna.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO

Distribution: SLO - CRO

Chorotype: SEU

83. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) complanatum* Heer, 1837

SLOVENIA

NW Slovenia, Vrsic 6 km N Trenta, 20.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

NW Slovenia, Kepa 19 km W Jesenica, 20.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj 1 ♀ (CTVR)

Daniel K. (1902): CRO – Croatia (without locality).

Apfelbeck (1904): CRO - Agram.

Müller (1926): SLO – Val Vrata (nel gruppo del Tricorno), Bochnia.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Kamniška Bistrica, Kamniška Bistrica

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO (Zagreb)

Distribution: SLO – CRO

Chorotype: CEU

84. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) concoeruleum* Netolitzky, 1943

SLOVENIA

Slov., Kranj, Kokra, 17.VI.1940, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(MB)

Daniel K. (1902 sub *coeruleum* Serville): CRO – Knin; BH – Sarajewo (Zeljeznica), Stolac, Konjica; MTG – Castelnuovo, Cattaro.

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *coeruleus* Serv.): BH – Umgebung von Sarajevo, Konjica, Drežnica, Mostar, Stolac; CRO – Knin; MTG – Rjeka, Castelnuovo, Cattaro.

Bonavita & Vigna (1993): SLO – S. Lucia di Tol., Slap; BH – Iglartal; MTG – Vruja, Ursprung, Montenegro mer.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *coeruleum*): CRO – BH - SB (Strbce) – MTG - NMA

Čurčić et al. (2007 sub *coeruleum*): the localities of Serbia reported for *coeruleum* have to refer to this species (Bonavita & Vigna Taglianti, 1993).

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Distribution: SLO - CRO – BH - SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: SEU

85. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) conforme* Dejean, 1831

SLOVENIA

Styria mer., Solcava, V.1930, leg. Cepic, 1 ♀!(MB)

NW Slovenia, Kepa 19 km W Jesenica, 20.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Slovenia, Bovec, 4-500, 2.VII.1974, Leg. Etonti, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Čevljanović bei Sarajevo, Konjica; MTG – Rjeka.

Netolitzky & Saint-Claire Deville (1915): SLO – Moistrana, Savicafall, Wochein, Flitsch-Karfreit; BH – Sarajewo, (Apfelbeck, 1904: Konjica a. d. Narenta), Igbartal, Čevljanović; MTG – (Apfelbeck, 1904: Rjeka).

Müller (1926): SLO –Bochnia (alla sorgente della Savizza), Val Vrata,

Moistrana.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Boka pri Bovcu; Kamniška Bistrica, Kamniška Bistrica.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – BH – MTG

Guéorguiev (2011): CRO

Distribution: SLO – CRO -BH - MTG

Chorotype: CEU

86. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) fasciolatum* (Duftschmid, 1812)

Reitter (1885): BH - “am Ufer der Bosna”.

Apfelbeck (1902a): BH – Vrbas-ufer bei Gornji Vakuf

Daniel K. (1902b): CRO - Pakrac (Slavonien)

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - CRO (Pakrac) - BH (B) - MTG (Rijeka Crnojevića)

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – two localities from Matić (1922)

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB - MTG

Chorotype: CEU

Notes. The localities and data reported for CRO, BH, SB and MTG before the review of Bonavita & Vigna Taglianti (1993), could refer to other species, and need to be confirmed.

87. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) geniculatum* Heer, 1837

ssp. *geniculatum* (Heer, 1837)

SLOVENIA

Maribor, Lovrenško jez., 16.VIII.1984, leg. G. Colombetta, 1 ♀ imm.!(Col)

Slo, Ledine, Kr, Jezersko, 16.V.1999, leg. G. Colombetta, 1 ♀!(Col)

NW Slovenia, Kepa 19 km W Jesenica, 20.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj 1♂ (CTVR)

SERBIA

Srbija, Kosovo, Šar Planina, Suva reka, Govedarska pećina, 23.VII.1995, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Šar Planina, Čop, m 1000, 16.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Šar planina, Durlav potok, nm 1500m, 20.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 5 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Kopaonik, 11.V.1976, leg G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Homoljske planine, Ceremošnjaja, nm 600m, 6.VI-27.VI.1998, leg. N. Ilić, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Šar planina, Durlav Potok, nm 1700 m, 20.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, Pljevlja, Kaluderovići, Klisura Sutjeske, 24.VIII.1995, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂ imm., 1 ♀!(Dpa)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonia, Šar pl., Suva Reka m 1200, 23.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Macedonia, Sar Planina, Popova Šapka, 27-28.VI.1965 G. Pozzi Como, 2 ♀♀ (CTVR)

Daniel K. (1902): BH – Tatra, Sarajewo (Pazarić, Trnovo), Bjelašnica planina, treskavica planina, Ivan planina, Han Koprionica, Stavljan Suha; SB – Stara planina; MTG – Rjeka.

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *Redtenbacheri*): BH – Umgebung von Sarajevo: Pazarić, Trnovo, Ivan-, Treskavica- und Bjelašnica planina, Han Koprivnica bei Kupreš, Stavljan, Sucha im Volujak-Gebiet; MTG – Rjeka.

Netolitzky (1915 sub *Redtenbacheri*): BH – Vranplanina, Sarajewo und Ljubeten, Igbartal; SB – Rambousek.

Müller (1926): SLO – Aidussina (alla sorgente del Hubel), Porezen; CRO – dint. Fiume, Val Recina.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994): CRO (Da, Konavlje) - SLO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – Popova Šapka

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: EUR

88. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkyi) leonhardi* Netolitzky, 1909

BOSNIA HERZEGOVINA

Herzegovina, Jablanica, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Netolitzky (1943): BH (Prosor e Jablanica).

Drovenik & Peks (1999): BH

Distribution: BH

Chorotype: SEU (BALK)

89. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) longipes* K. Daniel, 1902

Müller (1926): SLO – Bochnia, alla sorgente della Savizza.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Logarska dolina, Savinja; Kamniška Bistrica, Kamniška Bistrica.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO

Distribution: SLO

Chorotype: CEU

90. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) pseudascendens* Manderbach & Müller-Motzfeld, 2004

Neri (2016): MTG – Castelnuovo.

Distribution: MTG

Chorotype: CEU

91. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) relictum* Apfelbeck, 1904

Daniel K. (1902): BH – Ivan planina und Ingman planina bei Sarajevo.

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *complanatum relictum*): BH – Igman- und Ivan planina bei Sarajevo.

Netolitzky (1943): BH (Igman, Ivan-planina, Igbartäl), MTG, SB (Zljeb-Planina)

Meschnigg (1947): NMA – Ljuboten.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): BH - SB (Strbce) -MTG - NMA (Ljuboten)

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - Ljuboten

Distribution: CRO - BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: TUE

Notes. Vigna Taglianti (2004) mentions this species also for CRO, but we don't know bibliographic data.

92. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) rhodopense* Apfelbeck, 1902

SERBIA

- Kosovo, Šar planina, Brezovica, 14.7. 1997, 1 ♂, J. Prouza lgt.!(Reb)
Kosovo, Štrpec, 2.7. 1985, 3 ♂, 2 ♀, M. + J. Hladilovi lgt.!(Reb)
Serbia, Šar planina, 14.7.1997, 1 ♂, J. Prouza lgt.!(Reb)
Serbia, Šar planina, Nerod. Brezovica, Ririberg Mt., 14.7. 1997, 3 ♂, 2 ♀, P. Moravec lgt.!(Reb)
Serbia, Šar planina, Nerod. Brezovica, Ririberg Mt., 14.7. 1997, 2 ♂♂, M. Jaroš lgt.!(Reb, CTVR)
Serbia, Šar planina, Nerod. Brezovica, Ririberg Mt., 14.7. 1997, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀, V. Zieris lgt.!(Reb, CTVR)

NORTH MACEDONIA

- Macedonia, Šar. pl. Mts.: Popova Šapka - Δ, Ceripašin vrv, 1900 – 2300 m, 1 ♂, 19.6. 2008, L. Blažej lgt.!(Reb)

Netolitzky (1943): SB

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SB (Strpce) – MTG - NMA

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – Štrpce

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): MA: many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – more localities

Neri & Toledano (2021): MTG

Distribution: SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: SEU (BALK)

93. *B. (Bembidionetolitzkyi) tibiale* (Duftschmid, 1812)

SLOVENIA

- Slovenia, Goričane, 23.IV.1967, leg. Drioli, 1♂, 1♀!(Bon)
Slovenija, Bohinjsko jezero, 4.VII.1933, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1♀!(Dpa)
M. Jalovec, Tamar 1200 m, 11.VI.1988, leg. G. Colombetta, 2♂♂, 5♀♀!(Col)
Rakov, Škocjan, 31.V.1987, leg. G. Colombetta, 1♂!(Col)
NW Slovenia, Mts. Kolovrat, 20.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj, 1♀ (CTVR)

CROATIA

- Cro., Brod Moravica, 11.VII.1931, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1♂ imm., 1♀ imm.!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

- Bijelašnica Planina Bos, m 1200, 13.VII.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller, 3♂♂, 1♀!(Dpa)

SERBIA

- Srbija, Jastrebac, Ravnište, m 1200, 18.V.1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 1♂, 3♀♀!(Dpa)

Šar Planina, Čop, m 1000, 16.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Šar planina, Livadičko jezero, nm 2300m, 26.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Šar planina, Durlav potok, nm 1500m, 20.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Zvonačka banija, Prskalo, m 520, 25.IV.2002, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Zminje jezero 1490m, 11.VI.1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 3 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Mont., Durmitor, Škrčko Jezero, 2.VI.1958, leg. Stančić, 1 ♂!(MB)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonia, Šar pl., Suva Reka m 1200, 23.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Macedonia, Šar pl., Brezovica m 1000, 23.VI.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Daniel K. (1902): BH – Tatra, Sarajewo (Pazarić, Olovo, Vogošća), Ivan planina, Han Koprionica; SB – Serbien (without locality).

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Umgebung von Sarajevo, an Flussufern und Gebirgabächen bis 1000 Meter aufsteigend (Ivan planina), Han Koprivnica bei Bugojno, Vakuf bei Celebić, Gornji Vakuf am Vrbas, Konjica; MTG – Podgorica, Castelnuovo; SB – without locality in coll. Hofmuseum Wien.

Müller (1926): SLO – Plezzo (spec. lungo il torrente Pluzna), al lago del M. Nero, Aidussina, Nevoso; CRO – Nevoso, Clana.

Netolitzky (1912): SLO – Tolmein, Laibach [Lubiana], CRO – Agram [Zagabria], Velebit (G. Müller); BH – SB – MC – Usküb [Skopje]

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Ćurčić & Stanković (2011): SB - Nitva; Prekopac, Banovo Polje; Široka Bara

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: EUR

94. *B. (Bembidionetolitzky) varicolor* (Fabricius, 1803)
ssp. *varicolor* (Fabricius, 1803)

SLOVENIA

Slovenija, Bovec, 4-500, 2.VII.1974, Leg. Etonti, 1♂ (CTVR)

Slovenien, Kranjska Gora, 700m, 10.VII.1986, leg. Günther, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

SERBIA

Srbija, pl. Beljanica, klisura Čemernice, 2

6.VI.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Zvonačka banija, Prskalo, nm m 520, 25.IV.2002, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Bos., Bjelašnica, Tarčin-Lanište, m 700-1200, 15.VII.1931, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, Canyon of river Tara, Djurdevica Tara, Splavište 500m, 27.06.1985, leg. D. Pavičević 1 ex!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *tricolor*): BH – Sarajevo, Pazarić, Džile bei Vlasenica, Konjica a.d. Narenta; SB – Majdan Kutšaina.

Netolitzky F. & Saint-Claire Deville J., 1914b (sub *tricolor*): SLO – Tolmein, Wochem, Moistrana und Flitsch-Kerfreit, Loke und Vreme a.d. Reka, Bresovica; CRO – Untertribusa, Dinaraplanina; BH – Travnik, Zavidovic, Igbartal; MTG – Maglic; SB – Majdan Kučaina.

Müller (1926 sub *tricolor*): SLO – Plezzo (al torrente Pluzna), Tolmino, Volzana (Volče), Tribussa inf., Aidussina (valle del Vipacco), Loke e Vreme al Timavo sup., Bresovizza, Moistrana, Bochinia; CRO – dint. Fiume, Val Recina.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *tricolor*): SLO – CRO - BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA - r. Treska, s. Matka.

Distribution: SLO – CRO - BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: EUR

subg. *Peryphiolus* Jeannel, 1941

95. *B. (Peryphiolus) monticola* Sturm, 1825

ssp. *monticola* Sturm, 1825

SLOVENIA

Styria mer., Solcava, V.1930, leg. Cepic, 1 ♀ imm.!(MB)

Slovenia, Bovec m. 500, 2.vii.1974, Leg. Etonti, 2 ♂♂ (CTVR)

CROATIA

Croatia, Zagreb, Sava, 2.VII.1952, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Vrata Dragajce, Vran pl., m 1400, 30.V.1932, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Sarajevo; Jaice; Konjica, Jablanica, Čapljina, Stolac.

Netolitzky & Saint-Claire Deville J. (1914a): SLO – Wochein, Mojstrana, Heidenschaft, Tolmein, Laibach, Illyr. Feistritz [Bisterza]; BH – Prozor, Mostar, Igbartal, Sarajevo, Jaice, Konjica, Jablanica, Stolac, Čapljina.

Müller (1926): SLO – Tolmino, Aidussina, Ribnica al Timavo sup., Bisterza; CRO – Val Recina pr. Fiume.

Depoli (1930): CRO – Carie [Harjje] (luoghi paludosi).

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Šklendrovec, Kum; Ruše, Drava.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO – BH – (Matka)

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – Peć

Guéorguiev (2011): MTG

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - more localities

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH – SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: EUR

subg. *Omoperlyphus* Netolitzky, 1931

96. *B. (Omoperlyphus) hypocrita* Dejean, 1831

ssp. hypocrita Dejean, 1831

Müller (1926): SLO – Aidussina (torrente Hubel), lungo il Risano.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO (Hubelj-Ajdovscina).

Distribution: SLO

Notes. This datum is not reported in Marggi et al. (2017).

ssp. illyricum Netolitzky, 1918

[without target] - 1 ♀ imm.!(MB)

CROATIA

- Solin D., 29.VIII.1930, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Solin D., 19.VII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)
Solin D., 24.VI.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Dalmacija, Solin, 29.VIII.1930, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa)
Mosor D., 2.IX.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Žrnovica D., 27.IX.1931, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)
Split D., 28.V.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(MB)
Croatia, Solin, 29.III.1930, leg. G. Nonveiller, 7 ♂♂!(Dpa, Bon)
Dalmatia, Val di Canali, (Pridvorje-Ljuta), 20-VI-1930, A. d'Orchymont, 1 ♀ (CTVR)
Croatia: S. Dalmatia, Konavle, Ljuta env., river and channels, 23.vi.2011, Leg. J. Cooter, 1 ♂ (CTVR)
SERBIA
Srbija, Beljanica, 28.V.1989, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA
Mostar Herz., V.1928, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂ imm., 3 ♀♀ (1 imm.)!(Dpa, Bon)
Buna-Blagaj H, Env. Mostar, 30.VI.1932, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)
MONTENEGRO
Crna Gora, Kotor, Škurda, 19.VIII.1957, leg G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Krupaquelle bei Sarajevo, Bregavaquelle bei Stolac; CRO – Dalmatien; MTG – Rjeka; SB – Bela Palanka, Kladovo.

Netolitzky (1943): Dalmazia.

Vysoký (1986): BH – Jablonica.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): CRO (Da) – BH – SB - MTG (Rijeka Crnojevica) - NMA (Belica-Brod)

Čurčić et al. (2007 sub *hypocrita*): SB – more localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - Skopje: r. Treska

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – Skopje: r. Treska

Distribution: CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: MED

97. *B. (Omoperypheus) semibraccatum* Netolitzky, 1911

Drovenik & Peks (1994): CRO (Da) – BH – SB – MTG
 Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – without precise locality

Distribution: CRO – BH – SB – MTG
 Chorotype: TUM (BAN)

98. *B. (Omoperypheus) steinbuehleri* Ganglbauer, 1891
 ssp. *steinbuehleri* Ganglbauer, 1891

CROATIA

Pola, leg. Weber, 1 ♀!(MB)

Croatia, Solin, 21.III.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 10 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(MB, Bon)

Dalmazia, Dubrovnik (Croazia), Is. Mrkan, 20-V-1964, G. Pozzi – Como, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1904): CRO – Ragusa [Dubrovnik]; MTG - Castelnuovo.

Müller (1926): CRO – Pola, Brioni, dint. di Fiume.

Netolitzky (1943): Pola, Ragusa, Dalmazia.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): CRO - MTG (adriatisches Küste)

Distribution: CRO - MTG
 Chorotype: MED

subg. *Ocydromus* Clairville, 1806

99. *B. (Ocydromus) atlanticum* Wollaston, 1854

ssp. *atlanticum* Wollaston, 1854

= *megaspilum* (Walker, 1871)

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015 sub *atlanticum megaspilum*): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016 sub *atlanticum megaspilum*): NMA – more localities

Distribution: NMA
 Chorotype: TUM

100. *B. (Ocydromus) decorum* (Panzer, 1799)

ssp. *decorum* (Panzer, 1799)

SLOVENIA

Slovenija, Robic, greto f. Natisone, 18/VIII/97, Leg. P. De Martin, 2 ♂♂ (CTVR)

CROATIA

YU, KRK, SUNA RIČINA R., 23.IV.1989, LEG. G. COLOMBETTA, 3 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀!(COL)
Horvatova špilja, HE Sklope, Kosinj, 27.VIII.2016, leg. Roman Ozimec., 1 ♀
imm.!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Srbija, Šar planina, Durlov Potok, nm 1700 m, 20.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević,
1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Vlaška planina, s. Dučevci, 9.V.2000, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Serbie orient., Env. de Niš, VI.1933, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, Pljevlja, Kaluderovići, Klisura Sutjeske, 21.VIII.1995, leg. M.
Popović, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Reitter (1885): BH - "am Ufer der Bosna".

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – gemein an Flüssen und Bächen; CRO – Knin; MTG – Rjeka, Castelnuovo, Cattaro; SB – Majdan Kutšaina, Straža planina bei Žagubica, Zaječar, Surdulica bei Vranja.

Müller (1926): SLO – Volzana (Volče), Tolmino e Plezzo lungo l'Isonzo, alla cascata della Savizza, lago di Raiibl, lungo il Recca di Ospo e il Risano, Losizze e S. Vito ai piedi del M. Re, val Branizza pr. S. Daniele, lungo il Timavo sup., presso S. Canziano, Naclo, Loke e Vreme, Roditti, Bresovizza; CRO – Liburnia (alle falde del M. Maggiore verso Vragna), Skrad, isola di Veglia pr. Besca.

Depoli (1930): CRO - Sappiane (in riva al ruscello nel polje).

Müller-Motzfeld (1986a): SLO – Krainburg [Kranj], Kankertal [Kokra-Dol.], Radna, St. Paul [?Umgebung Zalec], Gurkfeld [Videm-Krško], Laibach [Ljubljana], Mrzlica-Berge b. Tribovlje, Pettau [Ptuj], Maribor, Cilli [Celje], Savinjske Alpe, Sv. Jurij, Dobje, Podčetrtek-Sotla, Logar-Tal [?Slap. palenc.]; CRO – Skrad, Veglia Besca [Stara Baška], Leskov [? Leska Dol.], Velebit, Agram [Zagreb], Almissa [Omiš], Insel Rab, Dalmatia, Dinara plan., canale [? Dalm.]; SB – Fruska gora, Kuršumlie [Kuršumljia], Serbien; BH – Jablanica, Prozor, Banja stjena, Bosna-Tal, Priboj, Pole b. Sarajevo, Sarajevo, Mostar, Ilidža, Nemila, Majejica-geb., Trebević, Bosnia, Cajnica, Gorica plan sw Jajce, Teslić-Vlas, Derwent [Derventa], Igar-Tal, Trebinje, Donje Hrasno, Konjica-Umgebung, Herzegovina; MTG – Gusinje, Zljeb planina, Vruja-Ursprung,

Catarro [Kotor], Monastir Piva, Ivangrad, Castelnuovo [Herzegovini]; NMA-25 km nördlich Onrid, Skopje-Treskauf, Macedon.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – Ohrid: s. Belčišta

ssp. *bodemeyeri* K. Daniel & J. Daniel, 1902

Marggi et al. (2003): NMA

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - reported the data of Marggi et al. (2003)

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: TEM

101. *B. (Ocydromus) modestum* (Fabricius, 1801)

CROATIA

Zagreb Sava, 7.VI.1942, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂ imm., 1 ♀!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Srbija, Srem, Zemun, 20.V.1993, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent, Sarajevo, Višegrad.

Netolitzky (1914): SLO – Reichenburg, Radkersburg, Laibach; BH – Ilidže, Maglaj a. d. Bosna; SB – (Schaum, Ins. Deutschl., I. Bd.)

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Šalovci, Prekmurje.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – BH (B)

Guéorguiev (2011): BH

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - Mazedonien-Hudova am Vardar

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB - NMA

Chorotype: CEU

102. *B. (Ocydromus) siculum* Dejean, 1831

ssp. *smyrnense* Apfelbeck, 1904

CROATIA

Solin, 19.VII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa, Bon)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *siculum*): BH – Blidinje, Konjica, Stolac; CRO – Knin; MTG – Rjeka.

Müller-Motzfeld (1986a): CRO – Spalato, Savina, Krivosije; SB – Soplje; BH – Tisovica, Igar-Tal, Nevesinje, Stolac, Plagovo-Quelle; MTG – Gusinja, Zljeb-Planina, Vruja-Ursprung, Col du Sutorman, Petrovac, Castelnuovo [Herzegovini]; NMA – Dojran, Prespa – Buć-Gebirge.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *siculum siculum* (sic!) and *siculum smyrnense*): CRO (Knin, Becici) – BH (H) - MTG (Petrovac, Rumija) - NMA (Dojran, Bukovik)

Ćurčić et al. (2007 sub *siculum*): SB – Topli Dol (Matić, 1922)

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – more localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – more localities

Distribution: CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: TEM

103. *B. (Ocydromus) transsylvanicum* Bielz, 1852

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent; CRO – Agram, Tuškanec.

Netolitzky (1943): CRO.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): CRO (Zagreb) - BH (B. Derventa)

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities

Marggi & Kofler (2014): SLO: Velika Pirešica; Carniolia, Blanca-arto, stajen gr.

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH - SB

Chorotype: CEU

subg. *Peryphus* Dejean, 1821

104. *B. (Peryphus) andreae* (Fabricius, 1787)

Müller (1926 sub *occidentale*): SLO – Decani, lungo il Risano; CRO – Levade (sulle sponde argillose del Quieto), Arsa.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *occidentale*): SLO (Istra) – CRO (Dolina Mirne)

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities.

Distribution: SLO – CRO

Chorotype: WME

105. *B. (Peryphus) bruxellense* Wesmael, 1835

Drovenik & Peks (1999): SB (Beograd)
 Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities

Distribution: SB
 Chorotype: PAL

106. *B. (Peryphus) bualei* Jacquelin du Val, 1852

ssp. *bualei* Jacquelin du Val, 1852
 = *albanicum* J. Müller, 1935

SLOVENIJA

NW Slovenia, Kepa 19 km W Jesenica, 20.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

Slovenia, Julian Alps, Mangart Mts. Range, ca 400 m NE fork Mangart Pass road - Predil pass road, 1130 m, 46°25'30.5" N / 13°35'49.9" E, (brook bank, gravel), 14.VII.2013 Wrase & Laser [15A], 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Slovenia Julian Alps, Soca valley, Soca river 1 km SE Zaga vill. 334 m, 46°17'57.0" N / 13°29'42.3 E", (embankment forest, on dry sand), 19.VII.2013 Wrase & Laser [24A]. 1 ♂ (CTVR)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, Prokletije Mts., Bukumirsko jezero, 12.VI.1934, leg. P. Dabović, 2 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, Prokletije, Bukumirsko jezero, 29.VIII.1933, leg. P. Dabović, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Gevgelia Mace, 28.V.1957, leg. Nonveiller, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *Andreae*): BH – verbreitet; CRO – Knin; MTG – Rjeka, Podgorica; SB – Podžarevac, Surdulica, Kladovo.

Müller (1926 sub *Andreae Bualei*): SLO – Plezzo, Tolmino, Hermsburg; CRO – Lupolano, Val Recina.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *andreae bualei*): SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG; sub *andreae albanicum*: MTG (Titograd) - NMA

Coulon (2006): SLO –Kranjska Gora; MTG – Ohrid, Virpazar, Zaton.

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities.

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015 sub *andreae bualei*): many localities; sub *andreae albanicum*: NMA - some bibliographic data.

Hristovski et al. (2016 sub *cruciatum bualei*): NMA – many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG – NMA

Chorotype: ASE

107. *B. (Peryphus) distinguendum* Jacquelin du Val, 1852
ssp. *distinguendum* Jacquelin du Val, 1852

Distribution: SLO

Chorotype: TUE

Notes. Vigna Taglianti (2004) mentions this species from Slovenia, but we don't know the original data.

108. *B. (Peryphus) femoratum* Sturm, 1825
ssp. *femoratum* Sturm, 1825

19.V.57, 1 ♂!(MB)

CROATIA

Sinj Dalm., 28.IV.1914, leg. Novak, 2 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀ (2 imm.)(Dpa, Bon)

Zagreb Sava, 20.VI.1942, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Zagreb, Sava, 20.VI.1942, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Serb., Kusići, V. Gradište, 2.VIII.1954, leg. Stančić, 1 ♂ imm., 2 ♀♀ (1 imm.)(MB)

Požeženo, V. Gradište Serb., 22.V.1955, leg. Stančić, 1 f imm.!(MB)

Müller (1926): SLO – Aidussina; CRO – Sussak pr. Fiume.

Depoli (1930): CRO - Sussak.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO (Susak) - SB (Beograd) - NMA

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – Belgrade

Guéorguiev (2011): BH

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH - SB - NMA

Chorotype: SIE

109. *B. (Peryphus) incognitum* (G. Müller, 1931)

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO

Guéorguiev (2011): BH

Distribution: SLO - BH

Chorotype: CEU

110. *B. (Peryphus) subcostatum* Motschulsky, 1850

ssp. *vau* Netolitzky, 1913

= *javurkovae* Fassati, 1944

CROATIA

Sinj Dalm., 28.IV.1914, leg. Novak, 1 ♂ imm., 2 ♀♀ imm.!(Dpa)

Zagreb Sava, 20.VI.1942, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 5.VII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 5.VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Croatia, Split, 29.IV.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Split, 10.IV.1958, leg. G. Nonveiller, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Split, 29.IV.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Srbija, Žagubica, 8.V.1937, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, pl. Kopaonik, Karaman, 15.VII.1957, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, pl. Kopaonik, Svinjski Brod, 15.VII.1957, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kučevo, Homoljske planine, Ceremosnja, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kučevo, Homoljske planine, Ceremosnja, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Jastrebac, Ravnište, 1200 m, 18.V.1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Miroč pl., Kopana Glavica, 9.VII.1999, leg. M. Popović, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Srem, Zemun, Kej, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Beljanica, klisura Čemernice, 26.VI.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♂♂ imm., 3 ♀♀ (1 imm.)(Dpa)

Serbia, Pirot env. dol. riek., Jerme, na brehu, 28.IV.2002, leg. T. Jászay, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Goč, Dobre vode, nm 840 m, 28.IX.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Homoljske planine, Ceremošnja, nm 600 m, 25.IV.1992, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Žagubica, 7.V.1937, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kalna, Stanjinac, 17.X.2001, leg. M. Popović, 7 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Zvonačka Banja, Prskalo, nm 520 m, 25.IV.2002, leg. M. Popović, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Serb., Ponikve, V. Gradište, 24.IX.1954, leg. Stančić, 1 ♀!(MB)

- Serb., Kopaonik, 3.IX.1954, leg. Lazarević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Syrmiium Zemun, 12.VIII.1942, leg. Ing. Osterman, 1 ♀!(MB)
Serb., Zlatac pl., 25.V.1978, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)
Serb., Majdanpek, Jasikovo, Korkan m 905, 19.V.1979, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Serb., Kruševac, env. Obilicevo, 12.VII.1934, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)
Serbia, Kopaonik Mt. 1500 m, 13.VII.1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)
Srbija, Pirot, Klisura Jerme, 28.IV.2002, leg. M. Popović, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)
Srbija, Javor pl., Štitkovo, 12.V.2003, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Srbija, Krusevac, IV.1934, leg. G. Nonveiller, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Srbija, Tupižnica pl., Lenovac, Vrelo Bele reke, 24.VII.1999, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)
Srbija, Miroč pl., Kopaona glavica 500 m, 9.VII.1999, leg. M. Popović, 2 ♀♀ imm.!(Dpa)
BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA
Mlinište Bosn, 9.VIII.35, leg. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Herz., Mostar, Radobolje, 9.III.1923, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)
Herz., Mostar, Radobolje, 29.III.1923, leg. S. Svirčev, 3 ♂♂!(Dpa, Bon)
Buna-Blagaj Hc., Env. Mostar, 30.VI.1932, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂ imm.!(Dpa)
Hercegovina, Mostarsko blato, 8.IV.1923, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Bos., Banja Luka, 2.XI.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Herz., Mostar, 2.V.1926, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)
Mostar Herz., Radobolje, 29.III.1923, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)
Hercegovina, Mostar, IV.1927, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa)
Mostar Herz., 2.V.1928, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)
Mostar Herz., 20.V.1923, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂ imm.!(Dpa)
MONTENEGRO
Crna Gora, Prokletije Mts., Bukumirsko jezero, 12.VI.1934, leg. P. Dabović, 2 ex!(Dpa, Bon)
Crna Gora, Djurdjeva Tara, Splavište 500 m, 24. VI. 1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ex!(Dpa)
Crna Gora, Pljevlja, Kaluderovići, Klisura Sutjeske, 21.VIII.1995, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂!(Dpa)
Crna Gora, Becici p. Budva env., 1.-14.vii.2002, P. Bulirsch lgt., 1 ♂ (CTVR)
NORTH MACEDONIA
Macedonia, Klisura Radike, 18.IV.2000, leg. I. Karaman, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904) sub *ustulatum*: BH – gemein; MTG – Podgorica, Rjeka,

Cetinje; SB – Požarevac, Bela Palanka, Semendria, Negotin, Zaječar, Surdulica bei Vranja.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *subcostatum javurkovae*): SLO – SB – MTG – NMA

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – Peć

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA -many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO - BH – SB – MTG – NMA

Chorotype: TUE

Notes. The populations of this species need to be reviewed. We noticed that in Serbia and N. Macedonia occur specimens with the same characters as in the Italian populations: elytral sides more parallel and darkened, black pronotum, well delimited spots, especially the apical ones, with black central cross; specimens more darkened; antennal segments (except for the first one) dark-blackish. On the other hand, in Croatia, Serbia and Bosnia-Herzegovina occur specimens different from the Italian populations: elytral sides more rounded and less dark, dark-reddish (not black) pronotum, lighter elytra with more confused apical spots; central cross dark reddish; all the specimens more reddish; antennal segments (except for the first one) brownish, not blackish.

111. *B. (Peryphus) tetracolum* Say, 1823

ssp. *tetracolum* Say, 1823

SLOVENIA

Slovenija, Lago di Cerknica q.500, 19-20/V/90, Leg. P. De Martin, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀ (CTVR)

Slovenia Julian Alps, Soca valley, Soca river 1 km SE Zaga vill. 334 m, 46°17'57.0" N / 13°29'42.3 E", (embankment forest, on dry sand), 19.VII.2013 Wrase & Laser [24A]. 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Slovenia Julian Alps, Triglav Mts., Sava Bohinjka riv., 2 km ESE Nomenj vill. 487m, 46°17'18" N / 14°01'58 E",

(bank, in gravel), 11.VII.2013 Wrase & Laser [09]. 1 ♀ (CTVR)

CROATIA

Env. de Zagreb, Alluivo Save, 12.IV.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(MB)

Reitter (1885 sub *ustulatum* Lin.): BH - "am Ufer der Bosna".

Apfelbeck (1904): all localities reported sub *ustulatum* have to probably to refer to the following species.

Müller (1926 sub *ustulatum*): SLO - nel Vallone di Muggia alla Rosandra pr. Gorenji Konc e lungo il Recca d'Ospo; sull'altipiano pr. Comeno, Timavo sup. pr. S. Canziano, Liburnia (Hermsburg, Nevoso).

Depoli (1930 sub *ustulatum* L.): CRO - Clana (all'imboccatura della caverna), Vrata, Abbazia, Mlaca.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Čurčić & Stanković (2011): SB – Zovik

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – more localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG – NMA

Chorotype: PAL

Notes. This species, widely diffused on the Alps and C-Europe, is more rare in the southern areas. So, some old data could refer to the preceding species.

subg. *Euperyphus* Jeannel, 1941

112. *B. (Euperyphus) combustum* Ménétériés, 1832

ssp. *combustum* Ménétériés, 1832

Apfelbeck (1904): MTG – Rjeka.

Netolitzky (1916b): BH – Jablonica, Igbartal bei Konjica.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): BH (H) – MTG - NMA

Guéorguiev (2011): Kosovo

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - some bibliographic data.

Distribution: BH – SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: TUE

113. *B. (Euperyphus) eques* Sturm, 1825

Netolitzky (1916b): CRO – Vranja (sub var. *nobile* Rottembg.), Lupoglava, Cirkvenica.

Müller (1926): CRO – Vragana, dint. Fiume, Cirquenizza.

Depoli (1930): CRO - Cirkvenica

Vysoký (1986): CRO – Croatia.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *eues eques* and *eques nobile*): SLO (Karawanken, Maribor) - CRO (Umg. Rijeka, Crikvenica)

Distribution: SLO - CRO

Chorotype: CEU

114. *B. (Euperyphus) fluviatile* Dejean, 1831
 ssp. *fluviatile* Dejean, 1831

MONTENEGRO

Montenegro, Durmitor Mt. Žabljak 1450 m, 18.VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller,
 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Bosna bei Reljevo.

Netolitzky & Meyer (1939): SLO - Brezice u. Sv. Jurij b. Celje, Umg. V.
 Laibach, Medno, Steinbrück; CRO - Zagreb, Gunja a. Save; BH - Sarajevo,
 Glamoc.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO (Zidani most) - BH (B. Reljevo)

Notes. Species new for Montenegro.

ssp. *pyrrium* De Monte, 1956

CROATIA

Zagreb, Sava, 10.V.1942, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂ imm.!(Dpa)

Env. de Zagreb, Alluivo Save, 11.V.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

De Monte (1955): Agram (Zagabria)

Distribution: SLO – CRO - BH - MTG

Chorotype: TEM

Notes. The distributions of the ssp. *fluviatile* and ssp. *pyrrium* are inconsistent. All
 subspecies of *fluviatile* need to be reviewed.

115. *B. (Euperyphus) fulvipes* Sturm, 1827

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Pod Lubnikom, Selška Sora.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO

Distribution: SLO

Chorotype: CEU

116. *B. (Euperyphus) scapulare* Dejean, 1831
ssp. *scapulare* Dejean, 1831

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Iližde, Željez.Spf, 1 ♂, coll. Novak!(MB)

Apfelbeck (1902b sub *oblongum*): MTG – Rjeka, Podgorica; SB – Kladovo.
Apfelbeck (1904 sub *oblongum*): BH – Umgebung von Sarajevo, am Ufer der Miljačka und Željeznica, Čapljina, Domanović; MTG – Rjeka, Podgorica; SB – Kladovo.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *scapulare scapulare*): SLO (West) – BH - SB (Kladovo) – MTG - NMA

Čurčić et al. (2007 sub *scapulare*, sub *scapulare oblongum* and *scapulare scapulare*! Sic!): SB – Kladovo.

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - some bibliographic data.

Distribution: SLO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: SEU

117. *B. (Euperyphus) tergluense* Netolitzky, 1918

Müller (1926 sub *oblongum tergluense* Net.): SLO - tra Plezzo e Caporetto, Sava di Wurzen presso Mojstrana (ai piedi del Tricorno).

Netolitzky (1943): SLO (alle sorgenti della Sava, Moistrana)

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *scapulare tergluense*): SLO (Julische Alpen)

Distribution: SLO

Chorotype: SEU (ALPE)

118. *B. (Euperyphus) testaceum* (Duftschmid, 1812)
ssp. *testaceum* (Duftschmid, 1812)

SLOVENIA

Styria mer., Maribor, 7-Felber-928, leg. Kodric, 1 ♀!(MB)

CROATIA

Zagreb Croatia, Sava, 2.VII.1942, leg. Svirčev, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Env. De Zagreb, Alluivo Save, 12.IV.1941, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Zagreb, Sava, 2.VII.1942, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor Žabljak, Crno jezero 1425 m, 20. VII. 1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 9 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Žabljak 1500 m, 20. VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ex!(Dpa)

Montenegro, Durmitor, Mt. Žabljak 1450 m, 18.VII.1954, leg. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Reitter (1885): BH - "am Ufer der Bosna".

Apfelbeck (1902b): MTG – SB.

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Dervent, Umgebung von Sarajevo, Džile bei Vlasenica, Višegrad, Čapljina, Gabela; CRO – Knin; MTG – Durmitor Gebiet; SB – Požarevac, Suva planina, Stara planina, Straža pl. Bei Žagubica, Zaječar, Paraćin.

Müller (1926): SLO – Britof al Timavo sup.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Bled; Ruše, Drava.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - CRO (Da) – BH – SB - MTG (Durmitor) - NMA (Dojran)

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA -many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: EUR

subg. *Lymnaeum* Stephens, 1828

119. *Lymnaeum nigropiceum* (Marsham, 1802)

CROATIA

I. Brazza D., VI.1908, leg. Novak, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(MB)

Croazia, Trogir, Ris. Nat. Mlinice, pantano riva mare, vaglio alghe spiagg., 24.4.2006 leg. Tagliapietra, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

Müller (1926): CRO – Pola.

Netolitzky (1943): Istria, Dalmazia

Drovenik & Peks (1994): Cro (Istra, Da)

Neri & Magrini (2011): CRO - S. Pietro, is. Brazza; Istria, Oltra, San

Nicolò; Brazza; Baliani; Valle Oltra.

Distribution: CRO

Chorotype: MED

subg. *Ocyturanus* Müller-Motzfeld, 1986

120. *B. (Ocyturanus) balcanicum* Apfelbeck, 1899

CROATIA

Split D., Žrnovica, 3.IX.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀ imm!(MB)

SERBIA

Srbija, pl Kopaonik, Bačište 1600 m, 18.VII.1985, leg. G. Mesaroš, 3 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Kopaonik Serb., m 1700, 1.IX.1959, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀ (1 imm.)(Dpa, Bon)

Kopaonik, Pančičev Vrh., 2000 m, 2.VII.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Šar planina, Dolovi, m 2000, 24.VI.1995, leg. D. Pavičević 1 ♂ (Dpa)

Srbija, Šar planina, Durlov potok, nm 1500 m, 20.VII. 1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 4 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Rudnik, Ostrovica, 6.IV.1997, leg. S. Pešić, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kučevo, Homoljske planine, Ceremošnja, nm 600m, 6.VI-27.VI.1998, leg. N. Ilić, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Šar planina, Piribeg - Crvena karpa, nm 2100-2200m, 26.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kopaonik, Suvo Rudište, nm 1900m, 17.VII.1985, leg. A. Četković, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kopaonik, Suvo Rudište, 31.V.1998, leg. A. Četković, 18 ♂♂, 21 ♀♀(Dpa, Bon, All)

Srbija, pl. Kopaonik, 2.IX.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 11 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, pl. Kopaonik, Milanov vrh 2000 m, 20.VII.1956, leg. Dabovic, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Serbia, Kopaonik Mt. 1700 m, 22.IX.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 9 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Serbia, Sar Planina, Jazince - mt. Jezerce, 2000-2300m, 15.7.1997, P. Moravec lgt., 1 ♂ (CTVR)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, pl. Komovi 2300 m, 6.VII.1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, Prokletije 5.7.1982, Marijas 2400-2450 m, J. Janek lgt., 1 ♂ (CTVR)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonia, Sar planina, Piribeg, 2100, 26.VII.1995, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Makedonija, Pelister, nm 2600 m, 26.VIII.1955, leg G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Macedonia, 18.7.20, Mt. Baba Planina, Golemo Jezero env., V. Zieris lgt.,
2♂♂, 3♀♀ (CTVR)

Macedonia, Sar Planina, Popova Sapka – mt. Ceripasin, vrv 2000-2500m,
16.7.1997, V. Zieris lgt, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀ (CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Prenj palnina; SB – Kopaonik Gebirge bei Raška an
der Türkischen Grenze.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – CRO (Istra, Lupogav) - BH (H. Prenj) – SB
– MTG - NMA

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – Mt. Kopaonik; Raška.

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – many localities.

Distribution: SLO – CRO - BH – SB – MTG – NMA

Chorotype: SEU

121. *B. (Ocyturanus) iacobi* Neri, 2017

Neri (2017): NMA - Šar planina, Mts. Ceripašin, Bobinova stena

Distribution: NMA

Chorotype: SEU (BALK)

122. *B. (Ocyturanus) pindicum* Apfelbeck, 1901

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Vran planina.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): BH (H, Vran planina)

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – some bibliographic data.

Distribution: BH - NMA

Chorotype: SEU (BALK)

123. *B. (Ocyturanus) praeustum* Dejean, 1831

= *viridifluum* J. Müller, 1929

CROATIA

Dugopolje D., Kotlenice, 15.VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Split D., 4.VI.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Žrnovica D., 27.IX.1931, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Makarska D., Veliko Brdo, «Pudošica», 28.VIII.1933, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1

♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Imotski D., VII.1905, leg. Novak, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Gata D., VII.1911, leg. Novak, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 5.VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

YU, Krk, Suna Ričina R., 23.IV.1989, leg. G. Colombetta, 1 ♀!(Col)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, Prokletije Mts., Bukumirsko jezero, 12. VI.1934, leg. P. Dabović, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, Kotor, 19.VIII.1957, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Konjica, Mostar, Čapljina, Stolac, Bilek; CRO – Knin, „Dalmatien (nach Dejean l.c. häufig)“; MTG – Rjeka, Podgorica.

In Gridelli (1929): Müller (1921): CRO – Lovrana presso Fiume.

Müller (1926): CRO – Draga di Moschiena, Pinguento, Ospe.

Gridelli (1929): BH – Igbar Planina; NMA – pianura del fiume Vardar.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *praeustum praeustum* and *praeustum viridifluum*):

SLO (Osp) - CRO (Da, Istra) – BH – MTG - NMA (Dojran, Gevgelija)

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – more localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – Šar Planina: Turčin

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – Šar Planina: Turčin

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: MED

124. *B. (Ocyturanus) reiseri* Apfelbeck, 1902

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Vilina Čvrstnica, 16.VII.1927, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(MB)

Herzegovina, Plasa planina, Dr. Grabowsky, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀ (CTVR)

Herzegovina, Vran planina, Ad. Hoffmann, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

Herzegovina, Vran planina, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Bosnia, Vlastic, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1902a): BH - Cvrstnica planina

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Vran planina, Cvrstnica pl. Bei Jablanica, Plasa pl.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): BH (Cvrstnica. Plasa, Vran planina)

? ssp. *vransense* Apfelbeck, 1902

species incertae sedis (see Neri 2016)

Apfelbeck (1902a): BH - Vran planina

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Alpin in der Vran-planina an der herzegowinischen Grenze.

Netolitzky (1943): BH (Cvrstnica, Plasa- und Vran-Planina).

Drovenik & Peks (1994): BH (B. Vran planina)

Distribution: BH

Chorotype: SEU (BALK)

Notes. In an accurate study Neri (2016) states that *vranense* is synonym of *reiseri*, but he prefers to rank *vranense* as *incertae sedis* because he didn't see the type, which was not found.

125. *B. (Ocyturanus) signatipenne* Jacquelin du Val, 1852

Drovenik & Peks (1994): NMA (Dojran)

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – reported the only data of Drovenik & Peks (1994).

Distribution: NMA

Chorotype: TUM (BAN)

? *B. (Ocyturanus) tauricum frivaldszkyi* Csiki, 1928

This taxon (Marggi et al., 2017) doesn't occur in the Balkan. We don't know to which species the following data refers. See also Neri (2017).

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *plannipenne* (sic!) Duval): BH (H, Prej planina)

Drovenik & Peks (1999): BH (H, Prej planina)

subg. *Peryphanes* Jeannel, 1941

126. *B. (Peryphanes) brunnicorne* Dejean, 1831

SLOVENIA

Slovenia, Capodistria [=Koper], Pozza Valle di Stagnone, 22.V.2011, leg. Colombetta, 1 ♂!(Col)

CROATIA

Čibača, Dubrovnik D., 18.IV.1926, leg. Novak, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Šumet, Ragusa D., V.1914, leg. Mussapp, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)

Croatia: S. Dalmatia, Konavle, Ljuta env., river and channels, 23.vi.2011,
Leg. J. Cooter, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Bosnia, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, pl. Prokletije, Bukumirsko jezero, 12.VI.1934, leg. P. Dabović,
1 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, Kotor, Škurda, 19.VIII.1957, leg G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa,
Bon)

Crna Gora, Kotor, 19.VIII.1957, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Crna Gora, Becici p. Budva env., 1.-14.vii.2002, P. Bulirsch lgt., 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Montenegro; Budva, 2.-7.4.1972, C. Johnson, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – verbreitet; CRO – Dalmatien; MTG – Rjeka,
Sutorman.

Depoli (1930): CRO - Breghi sopra Abbazia.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - CRO (Da) - BH – MTG - NMA (Mavrovo)

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB – many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – Kočani: r. Barbošnica

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: EME

127. *B. (Peryphanes) castaneipenne* Jacquelin du Val, 1851

Distribution: BH

Chorotype: TUM (BAN)

Notes. Vigna Taglianti (2004) and Marggi et al. (2017) mention this species
from Bosnia-Herzegovina, but we don't know the original data.

128. *B. (Peryphanes) dalmatinum* Dejean, 1831

ssp. *dalmatinum* Dejean, 1831

= *Bembidium nitidulum hybridum* Apfelbeck, 1904

SLOVENIA

Cenomelj Slov, Žopenca, 21.V.1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

CROATIA

Croatia«Ledenica» pod., Brizom-Biokovo, 30.VI.1931, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♂

imm.!(Dpa)

Sinj Dalm, Ugljane, 26.IX.1933, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

K. Blaca D., 1.XI.1930, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Makarska D., 2.VI.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 6 ♂♂ (3 imm.), 4 ♀♀ (2 imm.)(Dpa, Bon)

Dugopolje D., Kotlenice, 15.VIII.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Split D., 28.V.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ♂♂ imm.!(Dpa, Bon)

Split D., Žrnovica, 3.IX.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Hrvatska, Velebit, Paklenica, Devnjača, 1.VIII.2001, leg. S. V. Karlo, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Env. De Zagreb, Podsused, 1.VI.1941, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 24.VI.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 24.VI.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂ imm.!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 5.VII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 3 ♂♂!(Dpa, Bon)

Croatia, Solin, 5.VIII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 19.VII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Croatia, Solin, 24.VI.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂ imm., 3 ♀♀ (1 imm.)(Dpa, Bon)

Dalmatia, Solin, 5.VII.1928, leg. G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Biokovo pl., m 1400, 4.VI.1929, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)

Istria, Labin, torr. Pecina, 22.VII.2008, leg. P. Bonavita, 7 ♂♂ (1 imm.), 3 ♀♀!(Bon)

Istria, Pontpićan, 31.VII.2008, leg. P. Bonavita, 1 ♀!(Bon)

Poljakova špilja HE Sklope, Kosinj, 28.IX.2016, leg. Roman Ozimec, 3 ♂♂ (2 imm), 4 ♀♀ imm.!(Dpa, Bon)

Dalmatia, Biokovo pl., F. Blühweiss, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

Croatia: S. Dalmatia, Konavle, Ljuta env., river and channels, 23.vi.2011, Leg. J. Cooter, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

SERBIA

Srbija, Niš, Kalafat, Cerje, 500 m, 10.VIII.1999, leg. D. Pavićević, 3 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Svrljiške Planine, Ribarska Korita, 940 m, 11.VII.1998, leg. M. Popović, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Tupižnica pl., Lasovo, 25.VII.1999, leg. M. Popović, 6 ♂♂!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Pešter, Tutin, pećina Ponara,, leg. M. Radin, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Pl. Avala, m 400, 5.V.1996, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srem, Zemun, Kej, 21.V.1986, leg. M. Popović, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srem, Zemun, Novi Grad, 9. X. 1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Tupižnica pl., Lasovo, 25.VII.1999, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Stara planina, Tri Lokve nm, 1300m, 9.VI.2000, M. Stevanović, 5 ♂♂

- imm., 7 ♀♀ imm.!(Dpa)
Srbija, Goč pl, Dobre Vode, nm 840m, 28.IX.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 5 ♂♂,
2 ♀♀!(Dpa)
Srbija, Homoljske planine, Ceremošnja, nm 600m, 6.VI-27.VI.1998, leg. N.
Plić, 2 ♂♂!(Dpa)
Srbija, Kragujevac, Gruža, 21.XII.1981, leg. S. Pešić, 1 ♂!(Dpa)
Srbija, Niš, Babička gora, Beli potok, nm 830 m, 7.VI.2000, leg. D. Pavičević,
2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)
Srbija, Bor, Crni vrh, 18.VII.1981, leg. G. Mesaroš, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀ (1 imm.)(Dpa)
Srbija, Topola, 5.VI.1989, leg. M. Popović, 6 imm.!(Dpa)
Srbija, Svrljiške planine, peć. Popšica, 480m, 18.VI.2001, leg. D. Pavičević, 8
♂♂, 4 ♀♀ (1 imm.)(Dpa, Bon)
Srbija, Niš, Kopajkošara, 18.VI.2001, leg. M. Popović, 1 ♂ imm.!(Dpa)
Srbija, Kalna, Stanjinac, 17.X.2001, leg. M. Popović, 7 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀!(MB, Bon)
Srbija, Zlatibor pl., s. Rakovica, 11.VIII.2002, leg. D. Pavičević, 4 ♂♂!(Dpa)
Srbija, Zlatibor pl., kod Pipalske, pećine, 10.VIII.2002, leg. D. Pavičević, 2
♂♂, 5 ♀♀ (1 imm.)(Dpa)
Srbija, Niš, Kalafat, Cerje, 500 m, jama Cejanska. propast, 15.IX.1999, leg.
M. Popović, 7 ♀♀!(Dpa)
Srbija, Stara planina, Škrveno, nv 1500 m, 15.V.2001, leg. M. Popović, 6 ♂♂,
6 ♀♀ (1 imm.)(Dpa, Bon)
Srbija, Guča, selo Rti, Rćanska reka, 19.VII.2002, leg. D. Pavičević, 1
♂♂!(Dpa)
Srbija, Guča, selo Rti, nv 500 m, 17.VII.2002, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂♂, 1
♀!(Dpa)
Serb., Babička Gora 720 m, 10.V.2000, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Srbija, Rajac, 20.VII.2002, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Serb., Jastrebac pl., m 1200, 5.IX.1954, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)
Srbija, Niš, Kalafat, Cerje, m 500, 17.IX.1999, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa)
Srbija, Env. Kragujevac, 15.IV.1938, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Srbija, Niš, Cerje, Cerjanska pec., 11.VI.2000, leg. M. Popović, 4 ♂♂ imm.,
2 ♀♀ imm.!(Dpa)
Srbija, Niš, Kravlje, 13.VI.2000, leg. M. Popović, 1 m imm., 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Srbija, Stara pl. Tri Lokve 1600 m, 3.VI.2000, leg. M. Popović, 2 ♂♂ imm.,
2 ♀♀ imm.!(Dpa)
Srbija, Kučajske planine., Sisevac, 29.IV.2000, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♀!(Dpa)
Serbia, Niš, Kalafat, Cerje 500 m, 2.VII.2000, leg. Pavičević, 1 ♂ imm., 2
♀♀ (1 imm.)(Dpa)
Serbia: Nis region, Suva Planina, 640 m, Babicka Gora, Kosuta, 5.vii.2006,
Leg. J. Cooter, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Mostar Herz., V.1928, leg. Svirčev, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)

Mostar Herz, 23.VI.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂ imm.!(Dpa)

Mlinište Bosn, 9.VIII.35, leg. Nonveiller, 1 ♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Hercegovina, Plasa planina, Donja Grabovica, 5.VIII.1927, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Herz., Mostar, V.1928, leg. S. Svirčev, 1 ♀ imm.!(Dpa)

Hercegovina, Mostar, 1.VIII.1927, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Vrata Dragajce, Vran pl., m 1400, 30.V.1932, leg. S. Svirčev, 11 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, kanjon reke Tare, Durdavica Tara, Splavište 500 m, 24. VI. 1985, leg. D. Pavićević 1 ex.!(Dpa)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonia, Sar Planina, Popova Sarpa, 27-28-vi.1965, G. Pozzi Como, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

Makedonia, Lac Ohrid, Radoliste, Source, 7.VI-1930, A. d'Orchymont, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Umgebung von Sarajevo in der Ebene, Hoch-Gebirge von Süd- und Zentral-Bosnien subalpin, Višegrad an der Drina, namentlich an grösseren Flüssen (Narenta) häufig...; CRO – Dalmatien; MTG – Cetinje, Rjeka, Podgorica, Sutorman, Durmitor; SB – Stara planina, Suva planina, Bela Palanka, Valjevo, Kučevo, Surdulica bei Vranja.

Netolitzky & Müller (1914): SLO – Laibach, Radna a. d. Save bei Lichtenwald [Sevnica]; CRO – Agram [Zagreb], Mošćenice bei Fiume, Pola, Zara, Koslovac, Kistanje, Kosore bei Vrlika, Sinj, Imotski, Spalato, Salona, Metkovič, Almissa, Ragusa, Budua, Knin und Pridvorje, Canale, Slivno; BH – Sarajevo, Ilidže, Ivanplanina, Trebevicgeb., Igmangeb., Gola Jahorinengeb., Travnik, Prozor und Makljenpaß, Jaice-Jezero, Celebić, Višegrad, Bugojno und Han Koprivnica, Brčka, Bosn. Brod, Mokrepoljane, Jablanica, Blidinjesee, Vranplanina, Mostar, Stolac, Čapljina, Domanović, Bilek, Nevesinje, Igar und Jablanica, Trebinje, Avtovac bei Gačko ; SB – teste Schaum; MTG – (Apfelbeck, 1904: Podgorica, Njeguši bei Cetinje).

Müller (1926): CRO – Pola, Moschiena pr. Laurana, Abbazia, Fiume, Draga, Buccari, Valici, Grohovo, Kostajnovica, isola di Arbe.

Depoli (1930): CRO – Valici, Lopazza (bosco), Grohovo, valle di Draga, Buccari, valle Kostajnovica.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *dalmatinum dalmatinum*): SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *hybridum*): MTG (Crno jczcro-Durmitor)
Ćurčić et al. (2007 sub *dalmatinum* and *dalmatinum dalmatinum!*): SB – many localities
Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA – many localities
Neri & Toledano (2016): Balkan peninsula....Dalmatia, Zara
Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA – many localities

Distribution: SLO – CRO – BH – SB – MTG - NMA

Chorotype: TUE

129. *B. (Peryphanes) deletum* Audinet-Serville, 1821
ssp. *deletum* Audinet-Serville, 1821

SLOVENIA

Slov., Krško, 6.V.1933, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Slov., Pungert, VII.1917, leg. Pretner, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

M. Jalovec, Tamar 1200 m, 11.VI.1988, leg. G. Colombetta, 6 ♂♂!(Col)

Slovenia, Selva di Ternova, 20.VIII.1989, leg. G. Colombetta, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Col)

Slovenija, Tolmin, Jama pod Smoganic, Most na Soci-S. Lucia, 9.V.1993, leg. G. Colombetta, 1 ♀!(Col)

Mačkovića, Jama, 30.V.1992, 1 ♂!(Col)

SLO, Bosco Pečovnik – Luce, 18.VII.1999, leg. G. Colombetta, 2 ♀♀!(Col)

Slovenia, Artvise, 1.XI.1982, leg. G. Colombetta, 1 ♀!(Col)

Slovenia, M. Nanos 1300 m, 27.III.1989, leg. G. Colombetta, 1 ♂!(Col)

Dolina Volča jama, Selva di Piro, 21.VI.1993, leg. G. Colombetta, 1 ♂!(Col)

Selva di Ternova, Slovenia (YU), Colombetta lg., 8.IX.83, 3 ♂♂!(Col)

Sella Mangart, Slovenija, Colombetta leg., 28.VIII.85, 1 ♂!(Col)

Slovenia, lago Bled, 14.VIII.73 m. 500, leg. Etonti, 1 ♂ (CTVR)

Slovenia, Most na Soci, 29.VI.1996, leg. Grottole, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

SW Slovenia, 5 km E Masun, Snežik env., 15.5.04, lgt. E. & P. Hajdaj, 1 ♀ (CTVR)

CROATIA

Cro., Tounj, Kipelj, 14.IV.1933, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Cr., Koralpe, VII.1925, leg. Všetěčka, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

SERBIA

Srem, pl Fruska Gora, Iriški Venac 490 m, 3.VI.1984. leg. D. Pavićević 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, pl Tara, Zaovine 1100m, 19. V. 1989, leg. D. Pavićević, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, pl Kopaonik, Karaman, 1900 m, 12.V. 1976, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1

ex!(Dpa)

Srbija, Radan Planina, Sokolovica, Bačije m 1000, 17.V.1989, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Srbija, Bobija planina, nm 1000m, 18.IV.1980, leg G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Homoljske planine, Ceremošnja, nm 600m, 6.VI-27.VI.1998, leg. N. Plić, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Beograd, Miljakovac 400 m, 8.V.1992, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Srbija, Kopaonik, 11.V.1976, leg G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Serb., Kopaonik m 1500, 22.VII.1956, leg. Stančić, 1 ♀!(MB)

Srbija Šar pl., Stojkova kuća, nm 1700 m, 19.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Serb., Povljen pl., Debelo Brdo 1000 m, 24.III.1979, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Serb., Bobija pl. 1000 m, 31.III.1979, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Srbija, Suva pl., 2.V.1953, leg. leg. Stančić, 1 ♀!(MB)

Serbia, Srem, Fruška Gora, 9.VI.1957, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Kopaonik pl., Bačije m 1000, 17.V.1989, leg. D. Pavičević, 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Serbia, Šar planina, "Molika" m 1800, 25.VII.1995, leg.. D. Pavičević 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀(Dpa, Bon)

BOSNIA-HERZEGOVINA

Mlinište Bos., 11.VIII.1935, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Bosna, Mlinište, 9.VIII.1935, leg G. Nonveiller, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Bijelašnica planina Bos, 700 m, 2.VII.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller, 4 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀!(Dpa, Bon)

Bjelašnica Bos. 1500 m, 2.VII.1932, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

MONTENEGRO

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Zabljak 1500 m, 25.VI.1986, leg. M. Popović, 15 ex!(Dpa, Bon)

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Zminje jezero 1490m, 26.VI.1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 6 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Crno jezero 1450m, 23. VI. 1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 13 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora,pl. Durmitor, Tepca 1300m,26.VI.1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ex!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl. Durmitor, Čurovac, 1300m, 26.VI.1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Crna Gora, pl. Komovi, nm 1800m, 8.VI.1935, leg G. Nonveiller, 1 ♂!(Dpa)

Mont., Durmitor, Todorov Do, 2.VII.1958, leg. Stančić, 2 ♀♀!(MB)

Crna Gora, Durmitor pl., Tepca m 1300, 26.VI.1985, leg. D. Pavičević, 2

♂♂!(Dpa, Bon)

Durmitor Mont., Todorov Do., 2.VII.1958, leg. G. Nonveiller, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

NORTH MACEDONIA

Macedonia, Šar planina, "Molika" m 1800, 25.VII.1995, leg. D. Pavičević, 1

♂, 2 ♀♀!(MB, Bon)

Reitter (1885 sub *nitidulum* Mrsh.): BH - "am Ufer der Bosna".

Apfelbeck (1904 sub *nitidulum*): CRO - Kapela; BH - Gebirge bei Sarajevo, hochalpin auf der Bjelašnica- und Treskavica planina, Gebirge bei Jaice, Hochgebirge bei Gornji Vekuf, zahlreich an Schneeflecken der Vranica planina, Uilica planina an der dalmatinischen Grenze.

Müller (1926): SLO - Nevoso, M. Nero di Piedicolle, Bochinia (Savizza, Mrzli Studenec), Porezen, Plava, Valle del Vipacco (Aidussina, Panoviz), Roditti; CRO - Mune, Liburnia (M. Maggiore, Viševica, Lič), Val Recina presso Fiume.

Depoli (1930): SLO - Nevoso (Valgiorgina), Svinsciachi; CRO - M. Maggiore (tra la foglia umida), Alpe Grande (presso la vetta), bosco di faggi tra Sappiane e Bergud, valle della Recina, valle Kostajnovica, Lič (campo), Viševica.

Drovenik (1994 sub *nitidulum*): SLO - more localities

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *nitidulum*): SLO - CRO - BH - SB - MTG

Čurčić et al. (2007): SB - many localities

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - many localities

Hristovski et al. (2016): NMA - Pelister: Viroi

Distribution: SLO - CRO - BH - SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: SIE

130. *B. (Peryphanes) grandipenne* Schaum, 1862

ssp. *grandipenne* Schaum, 1862

Drovenik & Peks (1994): MTG (Rumija) - NMA (Gevgelija)

Guéorguiev (2011): Kosovo

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - some bibliographic data.

Distribution: SB - MTG - NMA

Chorotype: TUM (BAN)

131. *B. (Peryphanes) italicum* De Monte, 1943

Drovenik & Peks (1994): Slo (Gorica, Ajdovscina)

Distribution: SLO

Chorotype: SEU

132. *B. (Peryphanes) latinum* Netolitzky, 1911

SLOVENIA

Slovenia VL1635, Kamnik Volcji, Potok, Arboretum, 23.V.2010, Colombetta lg., 1 ♀!(Col)

Slovenia, Ankaran, 2.VI.2015, Colombetta legit, 1 ♂ imm., 1 ♀ imm.!(Col)

Slovenia, Vremski Britof, riv. Reka, 7.5.2012, Holiš J. lgt., Rébl K. det., 1 ♂ (Reb)

Müller (1926): SLO –Val Vipacco, Tribussa, Na Mokrim, Panoviz, San Basso, torrente Hubel pr. Aidussina, Divaccia, S. Servolo nella Grotta dell'Arco naturale; CRO – lungo la Rosandra a Bagnoli, valle del Quietto presso Levade, Obrovo, Gradisce, Pinguente, Bisterza.

Drovenik & Peks (1994 sub *dalmatinum latinum* pars): SLO (West) – CRO (Istra)

Distribution: SLO – CRO

Chorotype: SEU

133. *B. (Peryphanes) milleri* Jacquelin du Val, 1852

ssp. *milleri* Jacquelin du Val, 1852

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Sarajevo; SB – Semlin [German name for Zemun].

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Podkraj pri Hrastniku

Ćurčić et al. (2007): SB – some localities

Neri & Toledano (2015): SLO - CRO - SB

ssp. *carpathicum* J. Müller, 1918

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO - CRO (Da) - BH (B) – MTG - NMA (Ovce pole).

Neri & Toledano (2015): SB

Notes. As reported by Hristovski and Guéorguiev (2015) and other authors,

Bembidion milleri does not occur in the Balkans and its records should be actually referred to *B. brunnicorne*. We agree with this interpretation, and we consider this species occurring only in the states reported by Neri & Toledano (2015).

Distribution: SLO – CRO – SB

Chorotype: CEU

134. *B. (Peryphanes) stephensii* Crotch, 1866

ssp. *stephensii* Crotch, 1866

SERBIA

Srbija, Homolje, Pećina Ceremošnja, 25.IV.1992, leg. M. Popovič, 1 ♀!(Dpa)

Apfelbeck (1904): BH – Umgebung von Sarajevo, Miljačkatal, Vučjaluka, Ivan planina, Krupatal bei Pazarič.

Müller (1926): SLO – Roditti, Castelnovo.

Netolitzky & Meyer (1936b): SLO – Maribor, Solcava, Celje; BH – Nemila-Bosnien; SB – Fruska Gora, Sirmien.

Drovenik (1994): SLO – Tacen, Sava.

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO – BH (B) – NMA (Pelister)

Hristovski & Guéorguiev (2015): NMA - more localities.

Distribution: SLO – BH – SB – NMA

Chorotype: EUR

subg. *Asioperlyphus* Vysoký, 1986

135. *B. (Asioperlyphus) lunatum* (Duftschmid, 1812)

Apfelbeck (1904): CRO – Agram [Zagreb]

Drovenik & Peks (1994): SLO (Maribor) - CRO (Zagreb)

Distribution: SLO - CRO

Chorotype: ASE

BIOGEOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS

The Bembidiina species currently known for the former Yugoslavia are 135, belonging to the following genera: *Sinechostictus* Motschulsky, 1864 (7 species), *Ocys* Stephens, 1828 (4), *Asaphidion* Gozis, 1886 (8), *Bembidion* Latreille, 1802

(117). The following species are cited for the first time:

Bembidion (Eupetedromus) starkii Schaum, 1860, is new for Slovenia.

B. (Philochthus) mannerheimii C.R. Sahlberg, 1827, *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya) brunoii* (Bonavita, 2001) and *B. (Ocydromus) modestum* (Fabricius, 1801) are new for Croatia.

Ocys quinquistriatus (Gyllenhal, 1810) and *B. (Emphanes) azurescens* Dalla Torre, 1877 are new for Serbia. *B. (Euperyphus) fluviatile fluviatile* Dejean, 1831 is new for Montenegro.

The greater number of species occurs in Slovenia (94 species), Croatia (89) and Bosnia-Herzegovina (87), while the lower number occurs in Montenegro (67) and N. Macedonia (66) (Tab. 1). In respect to the size of the territory of Balkan countries, Montenegro and Slovenia show the higher level of biodiversity (number of species/1000 km² = 4.85 and 4.64 respectively) (tab. 2), probably reflecting the environmental diversity, from Mediterranean coastal to the high mountains for Montenegro, and the central European position for Slovenia.

The bembidiofauna analysed with the examination of the fundamental chorotypes (Vigna Taglianti et al., 1993, 1999) shows a high value (44.5%, 60 species) of taxa with wide distribution (included TUM-BAN) in the Palaearctic region and (41.5 %, 56 species) of taxa with European distribution (included SEU-BALK) (fig. 5). But, while the first value generally increases from North to South, the last one decreases decisively along the same direction. Lower value (14.1%, 19 species) occurs for the species with Mediterranean distribution, with higher percent in countries with wide coastal areas (CRO, MTG) (tab. 3).

In particular, regarding the taxa with wide distribution (Palaearctic, Turano-European and Turano-Mediterranean) the number of species increases from North to South, with the minimum in Slovenia (7.4%, 7.4%, 1.1% respectively) and Croatia and the maximum in Montenegro and Macedonia (10.4%, 11.9%, 7.5%), while the Sibero-European species, more numerous in mountain countries (SLO, BH, SB), decrease in the countries with Mediterranean areas (CRO, MTG, NMA).

Regarding the species with European distribution, we can note the strong decrease of the Centraleuropean species from North (22.3% in SLO) to South (4,5 in NMA), while European and S-European species result almost unvaried in all countries.

As we could expect, the species with Mediterranean distribution are more numerous especially in the countries with wide coastal areas (CRO, MTG) (tab. 3).

About the species more representative from the biogeographical perspective, we have recognised two principal subchorotypes: BAN – Balkano-Anatolian, that combines species with a more or less wide distribution in the SE-Europa and Anatolia, and BALK – Balkan, that combines all the endemic Balkan species:

Ocys hoffmanni (Netolitzky, 1917), *Bembidion* (*Testedium*) *trebinjense* Apfelbeck, 1899, *B. (Ocyturanus)* *iacobi* Neri, 2017, *B. (Ocyturanus)* *pindicum* Apfelbeck, 1901, *B. (Ocyturanus)* *reiseri* Apfelbeck, 1902, *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya)* *brunoi*, *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya)* *leonhardi* Netolitzky, 1909, *B. (Bembidionetolitzkya)* *rhodopense* Apfelbeck, 1902. The main area of endemism seems to be the mountain massif of Bosnia-Herzegovina and N. Macedonia.

Balkan Peninsula was an important area of refuge during the glaciations, when numerous species migrated to warmer southern lands, and subsequently, during the interglacial periods, recolonized the northern lands (f.e. mesophilous, igrophilous and termophilous species). Also between Bembidiina we find some examples of this pasted dynamics in the Balkan peninsula, as *Sinechostictus* (*Sinechostictus*) *tarsicus* (Peyron, 1858), *Asaphidiom* *nebulosum balcanicum* Netolitzky, 1918, *Bembidion* (*Peryphanes*) *brunnicornis* Dejean, 1831, *B. (Peryphanes)* *dalmatinum* Dejean, 1831 (see Bonavita & Vigna Taglianti, 2005). On the other hand, some species with northern distribution (e. g. mesophilic or frigidophilic species) have relict populations occurring in refuge massifs, as *B. (Philochthus)* *mannerheimii*, *B. (Bembidion)* *humerales* Sturm, 1825, *B. (Testediolum)* *glaciale* Heer, 1837.

Tab. 1. Presence of species in the countries of former Yugoslavia and relative chorotypes.

		SLO	CRO	BH	SB	MTG	NMA	chorotype
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>semipunctatum</i>	X	X	X	X			ASE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>funigatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	ASE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>articulatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	ASE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>bualei</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	ASE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>lunatum</i>	X	X					ASE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>axillare</i>	X	X	X	X	X		CEM
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>minimum</i>			X	X	X		CEM
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>quadripustulatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	CEM
<i>Sinechostictus</i>	<i>decoratus</i>	X		X				CEU
<i>Sinechostictus</i>	<i>millerianus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	CEU
<i>Sinechostictus</i>	<i>ruficornis</i>	X						CEU
<i>Sinechostictus</i>	<i>stomoides</i>	X	X					CEU
<i>Sinechostictus</i>	<i>doderoi</i>	X	X	X	X		X	CEU
<i>Sinechostictus</i>	<i>inustum</i>	X						CEU
<i>Asaphidion</i>	<i>austriacum</i>	X						CEU
<i>Asaphidion</i>	<i>caraboides</i>	X						CEU

<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>starkii</i>	X	X	X				CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>glaciale</i>	X		X	X	X		CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>ascendens</i>	X	X	X				CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>complanatum</i>	X	X					CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>conforme</i>	X	X	X		X		CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>fasciolatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X		CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>longipes</i>	X						CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>pseudascendens</i>					X		CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>modestum</i>	X	X	X	X		X	CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>transsylvanicum</i>	X	X	X	X			CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>incognitum</i>	X		X				CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>eques</i>	X	X					CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>fulvipes</i>	X						CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>milleri</i>	X	X		X			CEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>splendidum</i>	X	X	X	X		X	EEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>decolor</i>		X	X	X	X		EME
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>subfasciatum</i>		X					EME
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>quadrifossulatum</i>						X	EME
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>vseteckai</i>		X	X	X	X	X	EME
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>brunnicorne</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	EME
<i>Ocys</i>	<i>harpaloides</i>	X	X	X	X	X		EUM
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>lunulatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	EUM
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>genei</i>	X	X		X			EUM
<i>Ocys</i>	<i>quinquestriatus</i>	X	X	X	X			EUR
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>neresheimeri</i>	X						EUR
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>gilvipes</i>				X			EUR
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>foraminosum</i>	X	X	X	X		X	EUR
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>pygmaeum</i>	X	X	X	X		X	EUR
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>laticolle</i>	X	X	X	X	X		EUR
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>geniculatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	EUR
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>tibiale</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	EUR
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>varicolor</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	EUR
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>monticola</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	EUR
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>testaceum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	EUR

<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>stephensii</i>	X		X	X		X	EUR
<i>Asaphidion</i>	<i>stierlini</i>						X	MED
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>tethys</i>		X	X	X	X		MED
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>iricolor</i>		X					MED
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>maculatum</i>		X	X	X		X	MED
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>ephippium</i>	X	X			X		MED
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>normannum</i>		X	X	X	X	X	MED
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>callosum</i>					X		MED
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>hypocrita</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	MED
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>steinbuehleri</i>		X			X		MED
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>nigropiceum</i>		X					MED
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>praeustum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	MED
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>varium</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	PAL
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>assimile</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	PAL
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>octomaculatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	PAL
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>quadrimaculatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	PAL
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>lampros</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	PAL
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>properans</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	PAL
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>bruxellense</i>				X			PAL
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>tetracolum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	PAL
<i>Ocys</i>	<i>reticulatus</i>	X	X	X	X		X	SEU
<i>Asaphidion</i>	<i>cyanicorne</i>		X					SEU
<i>Asaphidion</i>	<i>nebulosum</i>		X	X	X	X	X	SEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>bugnioni</i>	X	X					SEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>concoeruleum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	SEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>scapulare</i>	X		X	X	X	X	SEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>balcanicum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	SEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>italicum</i>	X						SEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>latinum</i>	X	X					SEU
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>magellense</i>	X						SEU (ALAP)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>friebi</i>	X	X					SEU (ALPE)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>julianum</i>	X						SEU (ALPE)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>tergluense</i>	X						SEU (ALPE)
<i>Ocys</i>	<i>hoffmanni</i>		X					SEU (BALK)

<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>trebinjense</i>			X				SEU (BALK)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>brunoi</i>		X	X		X		SEU (BALK)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>leonhardi</i>			X				SEU (BALK)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>rhodopense</i>				X	X	X	SEU (BALK)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>iacobi</i>						X	SEU (BALK)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>pindicum</i>			X			X	SEU (BALK)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>reiseri</i>			X				SEU (BALK)
<i>Asaphidion</i>	<i>flavipes</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	SIE
<i>Asaphidion</i>	<i>pallipes</i>	X		X	X			SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>dentellum</i>	X	X	X	X	X		SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>biguttatum</i>	X	X	X	X		X	SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>guttula</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>mannerheimii</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>obliquum</i>				X			SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>schueppelii</i>	X						SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>doris</i>	X	X	X	X			SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>tenellum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>humerale</i>		X	X				SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>striatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X		SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>argenteolum</i>	X	X					SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>litorale</i>	X		X	X	X	X	SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>prasinum</i>	X	X	X		X		SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>bipunctatum</i>	X		X	X	X	X	SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>femoratum</i>	X	X	X	X		X	SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>deletum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	SIE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>latiplaga</i>		X	X	X	X		TEM
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>punctulatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	TEM
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>decorum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	TEM
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>siculum</i>		X	X	X	X	X	TEM
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>fluviatile</i>	X	X	X		X		TEM
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>inoptatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	TUE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>aspericolle</i>	X	X					TUE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>azurescens</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	TUE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>quadricolle</i>	X		X	X		X	TUE

<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>caucasicum</i>			X	X	X	X	TUE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>relictum</i>		X	X	X	X	X	TUE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>distinguendum</i>	X						TUE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>subcostatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	TUE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>combustum</i>			X	X	X	X	TUE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>dalmatinum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	TUE
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>atlanticum</i>						X	TUM
<i>Sinechostictus</i>	<i>tarsicus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	TUM (BAN)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>retipenne</i>				X		X	TUM (BAN)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>rufimacula</i>						X	TUM (BAN)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>semibraccatum</i>		X	X	X	X		TUM (BAN)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>signatipenne</i>						X	TUM (BAN)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>castaneipenne</i>			X				TUM (BAN)
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>grandipenne</i>				X	X	X	TUM (BAN)
<i>Asaphidion</i>	<i>curtum</i>	X						WME
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>obtusum</i>				X			WME
<i>Bembidion</i>	<i>andreae</i>	X	X					WME
Total species		94	89	87	82	67	66	

Tab. 2. Relationship between number of species and area of distribution in the Balkan countries.

	N° species	area (km ²)	sp. / 1000 km ²
Montenegro	67	13812	4,85
Slovenia	94	20273	4,64
North Macedonia	66	25713	2,57
Albania	64	28748	2,23
Moldova	62	33846	1,83
Bosnia-Herzegovina	87	51209	1,70
Croatia	89	56594	1,57
Serbia	82	88361	0,93
Bulgaria	89	110994	0,80
Greece	98	131940	0,74
Romania	90	238391	0,38

Tab. 3. Chorotypes (%) for the countries of the former Yugoslavia (for almost all the acronyms of the chorotypes see Vigna Taglianti et al., 1992; 1999). BAN – Balkano-Anatolian; BALK – endemic Balkans.

	SLO	CRO	BH	SB	MTG	NMA
PAL	7,4	7,9	8,0	9,8	10,4	10,6
ASE	5,3	5,6	4,6	4,9	4,5	4,5
SIE	17,0	14,6	17,2	17,1	14,9	13,6
CEM	2,1	2,2	3,4	3,7	4,5	1,5
TEM	3,2	5,6	5,7	4,9	7,5	4,5
TUE	7,4	6,7	9,2	9,8	10,4	12,1
TUM						1,5
TUM (BAN)	1,1	2,2	3,4	4,9	4,5	7,6
EUM	3,2	3,4	2,3	3,7	3,0	1,5
<i>tot WIDE</i>	46,8	48,3	54,0	58,5	59,7	57,6
EUR	11,7	10,1	11,5	13,4	9,0	12,1
CEU	22,3	13,5	12,6	8,5	7,5	4,5
SEU	7,4	7,9	5,7	6,1	6,0	7,6
SEU (BALK)		2,2	5,7	1,2	3,0	4,5
SEU (ALPE)	3,2	1,1				
SEU (ALAP)	1,1					
EEU	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,2	0,0	1,5
<i>tot EUR</i>	46,8	36,0	36,8	30,5	25,4	30,3
MED	3,2	10,1	5,7	6,1	10,4	7,6
WME	2,1	1,1		1,2		
EME	1,1	4,5	3,4	3,7	4,5	4,5
<i>tot MED</i>	6,4	15,7	9,2	11,0	14,9	12,1

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We wish to thank: Augusto Vigna Taglianti (†), Gianni Allegro, Achille Casale, Giorgio Colombetta, Werner Marggi, Paolo Neri, Maurizio Pavesi, Karel Rébl and Luca Toledano that helped us by providing data or material in study; Aleksandra Zatezalo for the help in preparation of a part of the material; Paolo Neri for the useful comments and Luca Toledano for the careful review of the manuscript and for all the beautiful, as always, photos of the habitus.

Fig. 1. A, *Simechostictus millerianus* (Serbia, Arilije – Moravica); B, *S. tarsicus* (Italia, Friuli, Bordano, UD); C, *Bembidion subfasciatum* (Greece, Anfilochia); D, *B. quadricolle* (Iran, Zagros Mts., S Dashtijeh vill.). Scale: 1 mm.

Fig. 2. A, *Bembidion splendidum pincum* (Serbia, Niš); B, *B. trebinjense* (Herzegovina, Trebinje); C, *B. brunoi* (Greece, Meteora); D, *B. leonhardi* (Herzegovina, Jablanica).
Scale: 1 mm.

Fig. 3. A, *Bembidion rhodopense* (Greece, Macedonia, Voras Mts); B, *B. semibraccatum* (Bulgaria, Maglige); C, *B. transsylvanicum* (Romania, Mt. Pad, Craiului); D, *B. combustum* (Iran, Zagros Mts., S Dashtijeh vill.). Scale: 1 mm.

Fig. 4. A - *Bembidion reiseri* (Herzegovina, Plasa Planina); B- *B. pindicum* (Albania, Reg. Skodër, Theti N.P.). Scale: 1 mm.

Fig. 5. Principal chorotypes in the former Yugoslavia. WIDE – species with wide distribution; TUM (BAN) – species with distribution Balkano-Anatolian; EUROPEAN – species with European distribution ; SEU (BALK) – endemic species of Balkan; MEDITERRANEAN – species with Mediterranean distribution.

REFERENCES

- APFELBECK V. 1902a. Sieben neue Arten den Gattung *Bembidium* Latr. Von der Balkanhalbinsel. Munchener Koleopterologische Zeitschrift 1 [1902–1903]: 66–69. [DP: 10 June 1902]
- APFELBECK V. 1902b. Zur Kenntnis der palaearktischen Carabiden. Synonymische und zoogeographische Beiträge. Munchener Koleopterologische Zeitschrift 1[1902–1903]: 95–101. [DP: 10 June 1902]
- APFELBECK V. 1904. Die Käferfauna der Balkanhalbinsel, mit Berücksichtigung Klein-Asiens und der Insel Kreta. Erster Band. Familienreihe Caraboidea. Berlin: R. Friedländer und Sohn, ix + 422 1pp.
- BONAVITA P. 2001. Un nuovo *Ocydromus* (*Bembidionetolitzkya*) di Grecia (Coleoptera Carabidae). Fragmenta Entomologica XXXIII (1): 43–50.
- BONAVITA P, Vigna Taglianti A. 1993. Note sulle specie di *Ocydromus* (*Bembidionetolitzkya*) del gruppo *fasciolatus* (Coleoptera, Carabidae). Fragmenta entomologica, 25: 67–90.
- BONAVITA P, Vigna Taglianti A. 2005. Le Alpi orientali come zona di transizione nel popolamento dei bembidini (Coleoptera, Carabidae). Biogeographia 26: 203–228.
- BONAVITA P, Vigna Taglianti A. 2010. *Ocydromus* subg. *Nepha* Motschulsky, 1864: revisione tassonomica, filogenesi e biogeografia (Coleoptera Carabidae). Memorie della Società entomologica italiana 89: 7–180.
- COULON J. 2006. Révision des taxons d'Europe et du bassin méditerranéen occidental rattachés a *Bembidion* (*Peryphus*) *cruciatum* Dejean. (Coleoptera, Carabidae, Bembidiini). Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie (N.S.) 22: 327–350.
- ĆURČIĆ SB, Brajković MM, Ćurčić BPM. 2007. The Carabids of Serbia. Monographs XI. Institute of Zoology, Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, 1083 pp.
- ĆURČIĆ SB, Stanković M. 2011. The Ground Beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae) of the Zasavica Special Nature Reserve (Serbia). Acta Entomologica serbica 16(1/2): 61–79.
- CSIKI E. 1946. Die Käferfauna der Karpaten-Beckens. I. Band. Allgemeiner Teil und Caraboidea. Budapest, 798 pp.
- DANIEL K. 1902. Revision der mit *Bembidium fasciolatum* Dft. und *tibiale* Dft. Verwandten Arten aus dem mitteleuropäischen Faunengebiete. Münch. Koleopterol. Z. 1: 5–37.
- DANIEL K. 1903. Beiträge zur Kolepteren-Geographie. Münch. Koleopterol. Z. 1: 258–260.
- DE MONTE T. 1955. V. contributo alla conoscenza dei Bembidiini paleartici (Col.

- P. Bonavita and D. Pavićević: Catalogue of Bembidiina of former Yugoslavia 275 Car.). Atti del Museo Civico di Trieste 20: 177–186.
- DEPOLI G. 1930. I Coleotteri della Liburnia. Parte I: Adepaga – Palpicornia. “Fiume”, Rivista della società di Studi Fiumani VII: 73–150.
- DROVENIK B. 1994. Prispevek k Poznavanju Favne Rodu *Bembidion* Latreille, 1802, v Sloveniji (Coleoptera: Carabidae). Acta Entomologica Slovenica 2:31–41.
- DROVENIK B, Peks H. 1994. Catalogus faunae Carabiden der Balkanländer. Schwanfelder Coleopterologische Mitteilungen, Sonderheft I, 1–103. [Schwanfeld, Germany]
- DROVENIK B, Peks H. 1999. Catalogus faunae Carabiden der Balkanländer (Coleoptera, Carabidae). Schwanfelder Coleopterologische Mitteilungen, Sonderheft I (Schwanfeld), 2 Auflage, 1–123. [Schwanfeld, Germany]
- FOCARILE A. 1964. Gli *Asaphidion* del gruppo *flavipes* (L.), con particolare riguardo alla fauna italiana. Memorie della società entomologica italiana 43: 97–120.
- GRIDELLI E. 1929. Nota su alcuni *Bembidion* della fauna mediterranea. Bollettino della Società entomologica italiana 74-75: 108–118.
- GUÉORGUIEV B. 2011. New and interesting records of Carabid Beetles from South-East Europe, South-West and Central Asia, with taxonomic notes on Pterostichini and Zabryni (Coleoptera, Carabidae). Linzer biol. Beitr. 43/1: 501–547.
- HRISTOVSKI S, Guéorguiev B. 2015. Annotated catalogue of the carabid beetles of the Republic of Macedonia (Coleoptera: Carabidae). Zootaxa, 4002 (1): 001–190. ISBN 978-1-77557-768-3 (Online edition).
- HRISTOVSKI S, Mihajlova B, Guéorguiev B. 2016. Review of the ground beetles (Coleoptera, Carabidae) from Macedonia in the collection of the Macedonian Museum of Natural History. pp. 21–51. — In: Veleviski, M., Matevska, O., Nikolov, Z. (eds): Anniversary Proceedings (1926–2016): Ninety years of achievement by the Macedonian Museum of Natural History, Skopje, Macedonian Museum of Natural History, Skopje.
- HUBER C, Marggi W. 1997. Revision der *Bembidion*-Untergattung *Phyla* Motschulsky, 1844 (Coleoptera, Carabidae, Bembidiinae). Revue suisse de Zoologie 104 (4): 761–783.
- MADDISON D. 2012. Phylogeny of *Bembidion* and related ground beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae: Trechinae: Bembidiini: Bembidiina). Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution 63 (2012) 533–576.
- MARGGI W, Huber C, Müller-Motzfeld G, Hartmann M. 2003. Carabidae: Bembidiini: Bembidiina. In: Löbl I. & Smetana A. (eds)–Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Volume 1. Archostemata–Myxophaga–Adepaga. Apollo Books, Stenstrup, 819 pp.
- MARGGI W, Kofler B. 2014. *Bembidion* (*Ocydromus*) *transsylvanicum*

- bielzerstnachweise in Slowenien. *Acta entomologica slovenica* 22 (1): 87–92.
- MARGGI W, Toledano L, Neri P. 2017. *Bembidiina*. In: Löbl I. & Löbl D. (Eds): *Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Volume I. Archostemata – Myxophaga – Adephaga*. Second edition. – Brill, Leiden: 294–342.
- MATIĆ SK. 1922. *Fauna serbica. Coleoptera. I part. Tribe: Caraboidea*. Memorial of the Serbian Royal Academy, 57: 1–50. [in Serbian]
- MEYER P. 1950 *Bembidion*-Studien. *Entomologische Blätter* 45-46: 102–105.
- MESCHNIGG J. 1947. Two new *Bembidion* Latr. From the Balcans. *Časopis Československé Společnosti Entomologicke* 44 (3-4): 91–96.
- MÜLLER G. 1926. *I Coleotteri della Venezia Giulia. Catalogo Ragionato. Parte I: Adephaga*. Trieste, 305 pp.
- MÜLLER G. 1943. Su alcuni *Bembidion* della fauna italiana e mediterranea (Col. Carabidae). *Bollettino della Societa Entomologica Italiana* 75: 11–16.
- MÜLLER-MOTZFELD G. 1982. Zur Trennung von *Bembidion ruficorne* Sturm und *millerianum* Heyden (Col., Carabidae). *Entomologische Nachrichten und Berichte* 26: 121–125.
- MÜLLER-MOTZFELD G. 1986a. Die Gruppe des *Bembidion* (Subgenus: *Ocydromus* Clairv.) *decorum* Zenker (Coleoptera: Carabidae). *Deutsche entomologische Zeitschrift, N.F.*, 33 (3-5): 137–175.
- Müller-MOTZFELD G. 1986b. Über eine bishewr verkannte Rasse der *Bembidion* (*Emphanes*) *normannum* Dej. (Col., Carabidae) vom Balkan. *Entomologische Nachrichten und Berichte* 30: 261–263.
- Müller-Motzfeld G, Marggi W. 2009. Zur Trennung von *Bembidion* (*Philochthus*) *judaicum* J. R. Sahlberg, 1908 und *B. decolor* Apfelbeck, 1911 (Coleoptera Carabidae). *Entomologische Nachrichten und Berichte* 53 (2): 101–102.
- NERI P. 2016. Note tassonomiche e geografiche su *Bembidion* (*Bembidionetolitzkya*) *concoeruleum* Netolitzky, 1943 e *B. (B.) pseudoascendens* Manderbach & Müller-Motzfeld, 2004 (Insecta Coleoptera Carabidae Bembidiina). *Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*, 44: 117–126.
- NERI P. 2017. Descrizione di *Bembidion* (*Ocyturanus*) *iacobi* n.sp. di Macedonia e Grecia, e chiave d'identificazione del sottogenere nella Penisola Balcanica (Insecta: Coleoptera: Carabidae: Bembidiina). *Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*, 45: 75–86.
- NERI P, Bonavita P, Gudenzi I, Magrini P, Toledano L. 2011. *Bembidiina della fauna italo-corsa: chiavi di identificazione* (Insecta Coleoptera Carabidae). *Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*, 33: 1–183.
- NERI P, Magrini P. 2011. Note concernenti i *Bembidion* appartenenti al sottogenere *Lymnaeum* Stephens, 1828 (Insecta Coleoptera Carabidae). *Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*, 29 (2010): 135–154.

- P. Bonavita and D. Pavićević: Catalogue of Bembidiina of former Yugoslavia 277
- NERI P, GUDENZI I. 2013. Note sul genere *Bembidion* Latreille, 1802, sottogenere *Philochthus* Stephens, 1828 e descrizione di cinque nuove specie (Insecta Coleoptera Carabidae). Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna 38: 97–179
- NERI P, TOLEDANO L. 2015. Note sinonimiche e tassonomiche su *Bembidion* (*Peryphanes*) *dalmatinum rufoguttatum* Netolitzky, 1943, e *Bembidion* (*P.*) *milleri* du Val, 1852 e sue sottospecie (Insecta Coleoptera Carabidae). Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna 42: 173–183.
- NERI P, TOLEDANO L. 2016. Synonymic, taxonomic and geographical notes on *Bembidion* (*Peryphanes*) *dalmatinum hybridum* Apfelbeck, 1904, and *Bembidion* (*P.*) *adygorum* Belousov & Sokolov, 1996 (Coleoptera, Carabidae, Bembidiini). Entomologische Blätter und Coleoptera, 112: 269–273.
- NERI P, TOLEDANO L. 2021. Geographic and taxonomic notes, addenda and corrigenda on the subtribe Bembidiina Stephens, 1827 of the 2017 ‘Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera’ (Coleoptera, Carabidae, Bembidiina). In: Spence J, Casale A, Assmann T, Lieberr JK, Penev L (Eds) Systematic Zoology and Biodiversity Science: A tribute to Terry Erwin (1940–2020). ZooKeys 1044: 563–587. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1044.62593>
- NETOLITZKY F. 1912. Die Verbreitung von *Bembidion tibiale* Duft. Entomologische Blätter 8 (2), map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1913a. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion prasinum* Duft. Entomologische Blätter 9 (1/2), map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1913b. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion Starki* Schaum. Entomologische Blätter 9 (9/10), map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1914. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion modestum* F. Entomologische Blätter 10 (7/8) map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1915. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion Redtenbacheri* Dan. Entomologische Blätter 11 (10/12), map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1916a. Die Verbreitung des *Ocys harpaloides* Serv. Entomologische Blätter 12 (1/3), map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1916b. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion eques* Sturm. Entomologische Blätter 12, map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1917a. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion ephippium* Marsh. Entomologische Blätter 13 (4/6), map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1917b. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion laticolle* Duft. Entomologische Blätter 13 (7/9), map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1918a. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion striatum* F. Entomologische Blätter 14 (4/6), map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1918b. Die Verbreitung des *Asaphidion caraboides* Schrk. und

- seiner Rassen. Entomologische Blätter 14 (7/9), map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1923. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion pygmaeum* Fabr. Entomologische Blätter 19 (1), map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1926. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion decoratum* Duft. Entomologische Blätter 22 (2), map.
- NETOLITZKY F. 1942-1943. Bestimmungstabellen europäischer Käfer (9. Stück). II. Fam. Carabidae, Subfam. Bembidiinae. 66. Gattung: *Bembidion* Latr. Bestimmungstabelle der *Bembidion*-Arten des paläarktischen Gebietes. *Koleopterologische Rundschau*, 28 (1942): 29-68; 28 (1943a): 69-124; 29 (1943b): 1-70.
- NETOLITZKY F, Meyer P. 1932a. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion elongatum* Dej. und *B. tarsicum* Peyron. Entomologische Blätter 28 (4), 2 pp., map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Meyer P. 1932b. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion humerale* Strm. Entomologische Blätter 28, 1 p., map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Meyer P. 1932c. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion atrovioleaceum* Duf. (*stomoides* Dej.). Entomologische Blätter 28, 2 pp., map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Meyer P. 1932d. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion quadriguttatum* F. (*4-pustulatum* Serv.). Entomologische Blätter 28, 2 pp., map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Meyer P. 1933a. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion millerianum* Heyd. Entomologische Blätter 29, 1 p., map.
- NETOLITZKY F, & Meyer P. 1933b. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion (Trepanedoris) Doris* Panz. Entomologische Blätter 29, 2 pp., map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Meyer P. 1936a. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion splendidum* Strm. Entomologische Blätter 32 (1), 1 p., map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Meyer P. 1936b. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion stephensi* Crotch. Entomologische Blätter 32 (3), 1 p., map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Meyer P. 1937. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion Illigeri* Net. (*quadriguttatum* Ill.) und des *B. Genei* Küst. Entomologische Blätter 33 (3), 2 pp., map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Meyer P. 1938. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion (Semicampa) Schüppeli* Dej. Entomologische Blätter 34 (3): 145, map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Meyer P. 1939. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion fluviatile* Dej. Entomologische Blätter 35: 1 p., map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Müller G. 1914. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion dalmatinum* Dej. Entomologische Blätter 10 (5/6), map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Saint-Claire Deville J. 1913. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion foraminosum*. Entomologische Blätter 9 (5/6), map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Saint-Claire Deville J. 1914a. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion*

- P. Bonavita and D. Pavićević: Catalogue of Bembidiina of former Yugoslavia 279
monticola Sturm. Entomologische Blätter 10 (1/2), map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Saint-Claire Deville J. 1914b. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion tricolor*. Entomologische Blätter 10 (11/12), map.
- NETOLITZKY F, Saint-Claire Deville J. 1915. Die Verbreitung des *Bembidion conforme* Dej. Entomologische Blätter 11 (7/9), map.
- PADEWIETH M. 1907. La fauna degli insetti nei dintorni di Fiume. Bollettino del Club di Scienze Naturali in Fiume: 104–122.
- PETRIK A. 1958. Entomofauna Deliblatske pešcare. Rad vojvođanskih muzeja 7: 87–113.
- REITTER E. 1885. Coleopterologische Ergebnisse einer Excursion nach Bosnien im Mai 1884. Deutsche entomologische Zeitschrift 29 (1): 193–216
- SCHATZMAYR A. 1939. Appunti Coleotterologici II. Rivista di scienze Naturali “Natura” 30(4): 205–212.
- SCHWEIGER H. 1975. Neue *Asaphidion*-formen aus der verwandtschaft des *flavipes* L. (Col. Carabidae). Koleopterologische Rundschau, 52: 105–111
- VIGNA Taglianti A. 1993. Checklist delle specie della Fauna d’Italia. Coleoptera Archostemata, Adephaga 1 (Carabidae). *Edizioni Calderini*, Bologna, 1–51.
- VIGNA Taglianti A. 2004. Fauna Europea: Carabidae. In: Audisio P. (ed.), Fauna Europea: Coleoptera 2, Beetles. Fauna Europea 1.1, available from <http://www.faunaeur.org> [accessed September 2009 as version 1.3 of April 19th 2007]
- VIGNA Taglianti A, Audisio PA, Belfiore C, Biondi M, Bologna MA, Carpaneto GM, De Biase A, De Felici S, Piattella E, Racheli T, Zapparoli M, Zoia S. 1993. Riflessioni di gruppo sui corotipi fondamentali della fauna w-paleartica ed in particolare italiana. Biogeographia, Lavori della Società italiana di Biogeografia, (n.s.) 16 (1992): 159–179.
- VIGNA Taglianti A, Audisio PA, Biondi M, Bologna MA, Carpaneto GM, De Biase A, Fattorini S, Piattella E, Sindaco R, Venchi A, Zapparoli M. 1999. A proposal for a chorotype classification of the Near East fauna, in the framework of the Western Palearctic region. Biogeographia, Lavori della Società Italiana di Biogeografia, (n.s.) 20: 31–59.
- VYSOKÝ V. 1986. Contribution to the knowledge of genus *Bembidion* Latreille, 1802. Fauna Bohemiae Septentrionalis 11: 91–104.